

**UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES
OPEN UNIVERSITY**

MASTER OF DEVELOPMENT COMMUNICATION

MAYFLOR MARIE L. JUMAMIL

**DISASTER MEDIA TOOLS, COMMUNITY INFLUENCERS,
AND THEIR EFFECTIVENESS IN DISASTER RISK AND REDUCTION
MANAGEMENT IN TIWI, ALBAY**

Thesis Adviser:

JOANE A. SERRANO
Faculty of Information and Communication Studies

December 12, 2023

Permission of the classification of this academic work access is subject to the provisions of applicable laws, the provisions of the UP IPR policy, and any contractual obligations:

Invention (I)	☐ Yes or No ☒
Publication (P)	☐ Yes or No ☒
Confidential (C)	☐ Yes or No ☒
Free (F)	☒ Yes or No ☐

Student's signature:

Thesis adviser's signature:

University Permission Page

DISASTER MEDIA TOOLS, COMMUNITY INFLUENCERS, AND THEIR EFFECTIVENESS IN DISASTER RISK AND REDUCTION MANAGEMENT IN TIWI, ALBAY

"I hereby grant the University of the Philippines a non-exclusive, worldwide, royalty-free license to reproduce, publish, and publicly distribute copies of this Academic Work in whatever form subject to the provisions of applicable laws, the provisions of the UP IPR policy, and any contractual obligations, as well as more specific permission marking on the Title Page."

"I specifically allow the University to:

Specifically, I grant the following rights to the University:

- a. Upload a copy of the work in the theses database of the college/school/institute/department and any other databases available on the public internet*
- b. Publish the work in the college/school/institute/department journal, both in print and electronic or digital format and online; and*
- c. Give open access to the work, thus allowing "fair use" of the work by providing the Intellectual Property Code of the Philippines (Republic Act No. 8293), especially for teaching, scholarly, and research purposes.*

MAYFLOR MARIE L. JUMAMIL
Signature over Student Name and Date

Acceptance Page:

This paper prepared by **MAYFLOR MARIE L. JUMAMIL** with the title: “**DISASTER MEDIA TOOLS, COMMUNITY INFLUENCERS, AND THEIR EFFECTIVENESS IN DISASTER RISK AND REDUCTION MANAGEMENT IN TIWI, ALBAY**” is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Information and Communication Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Program.

JOANE V. SERRANO, PhD
Chair, Thesis Committee

12/23/2023

BENJAMINA PAULA G. FLOR, PhD
Member, Thesis Committee

12/12/2023

ALEXANDER G. FLOR, PhD
Member, Thesis Committee

12/12/2023

DIEGO SILANG S. MARANAN, PhD
Dean

Faculty of Information and Communication Studies

12 December 2023

Biographical Sketch

Going by the name of Mayflor Marie L. Jumamil, I am a regular government employee who is always on the run, juggling time and schedules for my office and family. As the lead staff for the public affairs unit in my current work, I am constantly dealing with various audiences applying communication strategies to aptly respond to them and maintain the good image of the agency. As a mother of four lovely kids and a wife to a government-employed husband who has a passion for real estate as a side hustle for most days, I always feel like going against time to do all that I wish to be done and enjoy life with these people that matter most to me.

My passion for gaining more knowledge and remaining in the world of academics has driven me to explore and pursue post-graduate education along with development communication. I am a staunch believer that for a country or a community to grow and enjoy its resources, people must always look for and consider changes that could bring positive outcomes. Thus, my engagement in this course has provided insights into how development is and should be communicated.

Outside my professional and academic endeavors, I enjoy cooking and preparing dishes for the family, and listening to good, soulful music. I enjoy nature and spend most of my free time in the garden. While enjoying these things, it would always be my impulse to know anything that tickles my curiosity, so Google and the internet would be a constant go-to reference for these “anythings.” I believe in the power of continuous learning and seeking opportunities to grow and expand my knowledge in life.

I was born in May which is why I am stubborn but down-to-earth, sensual, loyal, and reliable.

Completing this study for my post-graduate course beyond my prime adult years would be one of my greatest achievements so far and I am truly grateful to the Lord of the Universe!

Acknowledgment

My deepest gratitude to my Thesis Committee, Dr. Alexander Flor, Dr. Benjamina Flor, and Dr. Joane Serrano of the Faculty of Information and Communication Studies. Your academic and professional pieces of advice have provided the main structure of my study. Your immense consideration of this course requirement is more than I could wish for to help me finish my graduate studies journey, albeit took a long time to finally finish what I had started years back.

I could have not undertaken this journey too without the guidance and practical suggestions of my mentors whom I met while conducting the research and going about with my routine duties at work. Thank you, Dr. Magdalena Ocbian for the assistance extended when I was seeking guidance where I can begin with my research work. I am also truly grateful to my colleague, Dr. Charlie Tayas who was great in making everyone in the room love the tedious work of research. Your immense input greatly improved this paper; without your exemplars and kind, constant prodding, I would not have moved another inch for the many times I said, "I'm giving up!" You are all heaven-sent.

Words of thanks also to my co-workers in my previous and present jobs, friends, and families who have always reminded me of my value as a person in pursuit of my worth and meaning in life. Thank you also to all the persons who have made my life difficult, some are the direct cause of my stalling for some time in doing this research. You have made my journey significantly fulfilling. I am vindicated!

Lastly, I would be remiss in not mentioning my Lanuza-Jumamil family who

have always believed in me; and my Creator who was indeed the only source of wisdom, means, refuge, and motivation. Thank you for your angelic beings sent to me at the right moment when I needed them.

This endeavor would have not been made possible without you all. Thank you!

Dedication

This publication, in its entirety, is dedicated to Paul, who was with me from the beginning of my post-graduate journey as a constant support and inspiration in good times and bad times; and to my kids, Jeremy Paul, Paulyn May, Genesis May, and Marie Paula who will always look at the works of their mother in some way or another. May you find proof in this, that perseverance will always matter if you want to reach your dreams!

I love you all!

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Title Page	i
University Permission Page	ii
Acceptance Page	iii
Biographical Sketch	iv
Acknowledgment	vi
Dedication	viii
Table of Contents	ix
List of Tables	xi
List of Figures	xii
ABSTRACT	xiii
CHAPTER I: INTRODUCTION	1
Background of the Study	1
Statement of the Problem	11
Objectives of the Study	12
Significance of the Study	13
CHAPTER II: REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE	15
Communication Channels for Disaster Information	15
Information Technology and Disaster Management	22
Crisis Communication Attributes and Channels	25
Effective Channel and Tools for DRRM	34
The Albay DRRM Communication Framework	40
Synthesis	41
Theoretical Framework	43
Conceptual Framework	47
CHAPTER III: METHODOLOGY	50
Research Methodologies	50
Research Locale	52
Research Design	53
Data Gathering Instruments	54
Research Participants	55
Statistical Treatment and Design	56

CHAPTER IV: RESULTS AND DISCUSSION	58
Utilization of Disaster Media as Communication Channels/ Sources of Information by People Affected by the Disaster or TD Usman	58
Community Influencers	58
Disaster Media Channels Utilized by the Barangays including the Crisis Communication Framework or System Operating in Tiwi, Albay	64
Communication Tools/Devices Utilized by the Barangays Including the Crisis Communication Framework or System Operating in Tiwi Albay	70
Frequency of Use of Disaster Media Channels of Communications During Disaster and TD Usman	75
Communication Networks in the Municipality of Tiwi Albay that are Active in the Communities	78
Effectiveness of the Disaster Media Communication Channels used by Studied Barangays in Making Informed Decisions about DRRM in Tiwi in terms of 1) Timeliness; 2) Accuracy; 3) Relevance; and 4) Understandability	80
Problems or Challenges Encountered in Utilizing Disaster Media Channels and the Preparations Made for Maintaining Communication during Disasters	89
Preparations to Maintain Communication during Disasters	92
CHAPTER V: SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS	94
Summary of Findings	94
Conclusion	95
Recommendations	96
LITERATURE CITED	98
ANNEXES	
Annex A Questionnaire/Survey Form (English)	110
Annex B Questionnaire/Survey Form (Vernacular/Bicol-Albay)	118
Annex C Interview Documents	128

List of Tables

Table 1 Demographic characteristics of respondents	56
Table 2 Community influencers in the local communities of Tiwi, Albay	59
Table 3 Channels of communication/sources of information utilized during TD Usman	68
Table 4 Communication tools/devices utilized during TD Usman	73
Table 5 The respondents' frequency of use of disaster media channels of communication channels used during disasters	76
Table 6 The respondents' frequency of use of disaster media channels of communication during TD Usman	78
Table 7 Perceived effectiveness of the disaster media communication channels used by the study barangay in making informed decisions about DRRM in Tiwi, albay	81
Table 8 Perceived effectiveness of disaster media communication channels as to timeliness	82
Table 9 Perceived effectiveness of disaster media communication channels as to accuracy	85
Table 10 Perceived effectiveness of disaster media communication channels as to relevance	86
Table 11 Perceived effectiveness of disaster media communication channels as to understandability	88
Table 12 Problems or challenges encountered by the respondents in utilizing disaster media channels	90
Table 13 Preparations done by the study participants to maintain communications during disasters	92

List of Figures

Figure 1 Track of TD Usman	7
Figure 2 The SMCC Model from Jin, Liu, & Austin (2014)	44
Figure 3 The SMCC Model as conceptual framework in disaster communication in Tiwi, Albay	47
Figure 4 Aftermath scenarios of TD Usman in the localities of Tiwi, Albay	52
Figure 5 Community influencers in barangay Mayong and Maynonong	62
Figure 6 Summary of disaster media channels utilized by the barangays including the crisis communication framework or system operating in Tiwi, Albay	66
Figure 7 Communication tools/devices utilized during disaster communication framework or system operating in Brgy. Mayong and Maynonong	71
Figure 8 Communication networks in the municipality of Tiwi, Albay that are active in the communities	79

Abstract

Traditional and non-traditional media have become essential communication tools or channels for disseminating, informing, mobilizing, and coping with disaster-related information/messages. They provide real-time data and information for use in the different phases of the disaster to help spread awareness, support, and warnings in relief for victims. This study examines the various traditional and non-traditional communication tools available as disaster media. It identifies broadcast (TV and radio), print (newspaper), digital (cellphones), and social media as sources of disaster information/messages and their effectiveness for Tiwi, Albay's Disaster Risk and Reduction Management (DRRM). Six (6) sets of data were utilized to examine and determine the quad media as sources of information/messages. This includes the effectiveness of the identified sources of information as regards timeliness, accuracy, relevance, and understandability, the existing disaster media communication networks, the issues or challenges encountered by the residents and community during a disaster and during the Tropical Depression (TD) Usman, as well as the preparations made by the local government to maintain communication and activity of information channels.

This research employed an explanatory-sequential design using a mixed method approach by combining empirical surveys, focus group discussions, and key informant interviews with the select heads of the families and communities as the main respondents. It utilized stratified and purposive sampling from the most affected barangay and the least affected barangay as the strata. Purpose sampling was used in the selection of the study locale, with the town of Tiwi in Albay identified as the hardest-hit town during the occurrence of TD Usman.

The findings revealed that television and mobile phones are the most dominant disaster media tools or communication channels/information sources. Megaphones and radios are the most important communication tools and channels used. SMART and Globe remained the leading communication networks actively present and operating in the community. The local officials, local community, and family are the major community influencers and most influential people in the studied barangays.

Likewise, television, radio, cell phone/SMS, newspapers, social media, and its apps, such as FB, Twitter, and YouTube remain the important and effective disaster media platforms used. This is especially true in terms of ensuring the widest distribution, as it facilitates one-way information dissemination and creates opportunities for two-way dialogue and interaction between organizations, the public, and individuals. These disaster media platforms can also be used to identify both survivors and victims, particularly in helping the community to know if family and friends are safe. The disaster media platforms combined with mobile phones help report an accident precisely and send requests to the authorities for any form of assistance within the community.

Among the major problems or challenges encountered by the community, during a disaster and TD Usman, ranged from lack of communication networks or service providers to poor/slow internet connection, particularly when using the internet, cell phone, and social media. People can access the radio during a disaster due to the termination of an electrical power supply. Other challenges encountered are inefficient use of technology and other sources of information; difficulty in accessing disaster media tools due to expensive data connections; improper choice of communication channels, particularly in seeking information from neighbors and relatives; when radio, television, and social media fail, and there is a proliferation of fake news.

Finally, specific recommendations were offered to ensure the effective utilization of these disaster media tools. These included: the need to develop effective communication strategies and programs utilizing the suitable media tools among partner organizations with budget allocation and resources; local officials should carefully plan access points for any services in the anticipation of communication lines being damaged and should clearly and widely communicate the target location to save more lives and property; integrate the community influencers in a disaster-community-media-based communication infrastructure; develop social media emergency plans that will serve as the first source of reliable information by people affected by natural disasters or calamities to save more lives and properties; communities should be educated about the variety of alternative communication channels such as social media and its applications like YouTube, Twitter, Facebook and among others so they will empower and equip them with more information about communication alternatives and in order to adopt new technologies to suit their peculiar needs during a communication network paralysis; and the need to set up policies to ensure that the information or the message is adequately and accurately delivered; and that mechanisms are in place for people to give feedback or communicate to the authorities through social media, announcements on how to prepare for upcoming hazards needs to be immediately received, understood, and processed by the people who may be potentially affected.

Chapter I

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

The Philippines is reported to have the highest risk of natural disasters (Centre for Climate Change Economics and Policy Report, 2020). It is also considered one of the countries in Southeast Asia with the highest vulnerability to natural hazards and disasters such as typhoons, earthquakes, floods, volcanic eruptions, and landslides, due to its archipelago's location (Mina, 2021). The Philippine Statistics Authority (2020) reports that the Bicol region is one of the most vulnerable in the central part of the country.

Bicol region houses mountains and volcanoes, two of which are active volcanoes: Mt. Mayon in Albay and Mt. Bulusan in Sorsogon. Since the region lies within the Ring of Fire and faces directly toward the Pacific Ocean, strong typhoons are typically expected to trigger year-long floods and landslides in the most vulnerable areas. Earthquakes and tsunamis are also anticipated occurrences. As the climate changes, rainfall and temperature are also expected to increase. These climatic events invariably cause damage to life, property, infrastructure, and livelihoods, resulting in investment and economic losses across all sectors and industries in the region (Salceda, (2013).

As reported by ReliefWeb, Int. (2018), volcanic eruptions and tsunamis are some of the foremost geologically active areas in the Bicol region as they are related to the continental plate activity around the so-called "Ring of Fire." Apart from volcanic eruptions and tsunamis, climatic change, rising sea levels, and increasing natural disasters are also other factors expected to hit the region because of its vulnerability.

These threats are higher in terms of disaster risks, particularly in areas facing the Pacific Ocean, and those located in the Pacific Ring of Fire (Philippines: Disaster Reference Management Handbook, 2018).

Among the provinces in the Bicol Region, Albay was one of the worst hit by typhoons in 2006 as it experienced the most tragic events especially when Category 4 Typhoon Durian hit the country. Typhoon Durian, locally known as Typhoon Lei Ming, swept across the province of Albay, causing massive damage to life and property/infrastructure, especially in rural communities. Moreover, the Province of Albay has been reported by the Department of Environment and Natural Resources (DENR) and the Manila Observatory (Center for Environmental Geomatics – Manila Observatory (2005) in Tanvir (2014) as the typhoon highway of the Philippines, making Albay one of most vulnerable to disaster provinces in the country today (ReliefWeb, Int., 2018).

Tanvir (2014) has enumerated the disaster vulnerabilities of the province of Albay. Among these disaster vulnerabilities are as follows: (a) 19 to 21 occurrences of typhoons per year, of which 3-5 major direct hits on the Province of Albay; (b) About 198,000 houses are estimated to be threatened by wind destructions and thus at least 350,000 people need to be evacuated. (c) Mayon Volcano eruption also threatens three (3) cities and five (5) municipalities; (d) 127 villages or 11,000 to 12,000 families are threatened by landslides; (e) an estimated 300,000 people out of 1.2 million population is also threatened by the tsunami; and, (f) a total of eight (8) municipalities and two (2) cities are threatened by floods.

The Province of Albay is also vulnerable to climate weather-related risks as reported by Tanvir (2014). These risks may include typhoons, increased rainfall, El

Niño, rising temperatures, and geophysical hazards, including landslides, earthquakes, tsunamis, and volcanic eruptions. These reports were indeed true as in 2006, Albay was also one of the worst affected by typhoons among the provinces in Region V for it experienced the most tragic events (Reliefweb, Inc., 2006). The said typhoon is locally known as Typhoon Reming, which is reported to have swept most of the major geographical areas of the province and created massive damage to lives, properties, and infrastructures, most especially in rural communities.

According to Devex Editor (2018) reports, the typhoon brought heavy rainfall and mudflows from volcanic mud deposits that formed along the slopes of Mayon Volcano, undoubtedly burying surrounding communities and killing more than 600 people. This is considered the worst and so far, the most dramatic destruction ever, affecting livelihoods and property. Typhoon Reming was the turning point for the people and government officials in Albay as it paved the way for provincial governments to reassess their existing emergency preparedness and DRRM response policies and standards to determine if they can still meet current needs.

In 2020, three (3) typhoons, locally named Quinta, Rolly, and Ulysses also brought havoc to the first and second districts of Albay. Aside from the raging winds, deadly flooding from the slopes of the Mayon volcano, caused by torrential and heavy rains, resulted in losses in human and animal lives; and property and agriculture were devastated.

The Department of Science and Technology (DOST) with its Philippine Atmospheric, Geophysical and Astronomical Services Administration (PAGASA) and Philippine Institute of Volcanology and Seismology (PHIVOLCS) bureaus have begun upgrading their communication tools and ICT. This is to help maintain their integrity

as one of the highly trusted government agencies relied upon for information and advisories on meteorological and geological conditions, which are indicators of impending disasters. Nevertheless, in times of calamities and disasters, people are keen to find information via the different disaster media channels (i.e., traditional media, radio, and TV or social media), which are becoming very popular means of communication in far-flung areas.

Given the large amount of information sought before, during, and after a disaster, the disaster media as communication channels are considered very important. Identifying what specific information is needed, where to get the information, what media channels and communication tools should be utilized, and how are these relayed—correct and on time are salient for effective disaster risk and reduction management. This is deemed crucial to lessen the impact, prevent casualties and loss of lives, and avoid public panic, thus improving disaster response and mitigation and coordinating sectoral efforts during disasters.

Thus, the availability of disaster media tools and communication channels can provide an opportunity to broaden warnings to the affected communities, including the schools in times of emergencies. Some researchers (e.g., Robbins, n.d.) reported that disaster media tools have the potential to prevent communication breakdown by providing reliable and up-to-date sources of information or channels that could reinforce the diffusion of warning messages. The Office of Civil Defense (OCD) also considered disaster media tools as key informants and actors during the communication, response, and mitigation process. Aside from it, the other key informants and actors are the people or the public in general, the government

agencies, and other concerned offices with significant contributions to making DRRM efforts efficient and effective.

According to Medfors-Davis & Kapur (2014), people are still the priority, for they will always be caught at the center of any disaster. When faced with disasters, people manifest a common reaction: they want to know how to obtain assistance, what ongoing personal risks they face, and how they can protect themselves and their families.

The recent disasters that affected Bicol, specifically the provinces of Albay, Camarines Sur, and Sorsogon, have spurred concerns over the intensive use of disaster media channels, especially broadcast and social media. It is a known fact in Albay that over the years Mt. Mayon has shown an intermittent eruption without early signs or warnings, spewing ashes up in the sky after months of being at rest. These incidents generated public reactions in the local broadcast media and social media. However, local volcanologists and the office of the Albay DRRM Council have raised issues over the “sprouting of keyboard volcanologists” posting and spreading inaccurate advisories and false analyses on social media.

Moreover, it was observed that most of the time, the netizens quickly pick up this information and take it as valid. Even radio stations receive unvalidated information causing criticisms against the local bureaus of Phivolcs and the DRRM Council. It even somehow affected the evacuation and security protocols as some locales believed the fake information to be true. One common example of a situation leading to invalid assumptions of these keyboard volcanologists is the time when Mt. Mayon relaxes for a few days; leading to an assumption that the eruption will no longer continue or will already cease. However, the chief of the Office of PhiVolcs Bicol

rejected the claims and issued official advisories that the case is not so. It has also advised the media that advisories and analyses should be based on scientific and technical parameters observed by their office relative to the situation of the volcano (Recuenco, 2018).

Another disaster that caused a stir in the disaster media communication process was TD Usman. Despite the available emergency resources and in-placed protocols designed to prevent loss of lives and properties, five (5) provinces in the Region—Albay, Camarines Norte, Camarines Sur, Sorsogon, and Masbate were affected; with Albay and Camarines Sur recording the yet unparalleled casualties and damages for the year—days after the landfall of TD Usman. As TD Usman entered the Philippine Area of Responsibility on December 25, 2018, it started affecting the country and made landfall in Borongan, Samar.

Seemingly, the arrival of TD Usman boosted the northwest monsoon winds in Bicol, bringing heavy rains across the Southern Luzon and Eastern Visayas regions for several days. This triggered multiple landslides and widespread flooding. Some 191,600 people have been affected in regions IV-A, IV-B, V, and VIII. An updated report of the NDRRMC left a total of 122 deaths, and 105 of them were from Bicol (ReliefWeb, Int., 2018).

People and government officials have been pinpointing fingers on who is to be blamed for the incident. Some agencies said that because PAGASA had given a wrong and delayed forecast, people seemed unbothered and overlooked the risks of landslides and flooding brought by torrential rains even after the landfall of TD Usman. The allegedly delayed and “erroneous” advisories were contested by PAGASA which blamed the local government units for being too complacent to listen to the warnings.

TD Usman did not directly hit Bicol yet the region suffered tremendous casualties, and this is a first for the region. According to the United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (2019), people had only been relying upon the typhoon signal advisories and not on the rainfall warning, which could have been an indicator of possible flooding, and landslides.

The strength of TD Usman as reported by the United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs, caused massive devastation with 85 people dead, 20 missing, and 40 injured, following the landfall near Borongan, the capital of the province of Eastern Samar, on December 29, 2018. The severe devastation caused by TD Usman clearly shows the high vulnerability of the community.

The track of TD Usman is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1.

Track of TD Usman.

The two disastrous events (Mt. Mayon eruptions and TD Usman) have presented views on how disaster media tools as communication channels can play a vital role in disaster preparedness, response, and mitigation to prevent loss of lives and properties. Conceivably, the “erroneous” advisories and disinformation contributed to what happened in the community.

Bongo (2010) studied the available communication media as channels of disaster information in times of disaster in Zimbabwe. He reported that effective community-level dissemination of these media as channels of disaster information need to be localized by streamlining the “jargon” used in transmitting the information, as it impedes communication strategies to communities. This is one of the identified gaps in disaster communication and may have parallels with the communities’ situation in Bicol. Hence, disaster information and messages should indeed be clear and understandable to the intended recipients of the information.

Robbins (n.d.), in her article “Social Media in Disasters”, identified the various types of disaster media tools she believed can be complementary to disaster risk and crisis management strategy as it creates a synthesis of various social media content to help local governments, affected communities, and volunteers address emergency and disaster preparedness to make them more resilient to disasters.

In assisting the school during and after disaster crises, disaster media tools as channels of communication/information can be utilized to inform school heads, staff, teachers, and students to be more vigilant and prepared in case of emergencies and disasters. These disasters, whether natural (such as earthquakes, floods, typhoons, or landslides, among others) or man-made (like fire, chemical spills, bombs, etc.)

should be properly communicated to protect people from personal injury, loss of life, and the school property, infrastructures, and other facilities from possible damages.

Robbins (n.d.) also stressed that social networking can help affected communities enhance coordination between local government units, volunteers, and other emergency service providers. Content sharing social media as another communication channel can help the community identify images or videos for situational awareness, as well as document and report evolving crises in real-time. It can also encourage dialogues between local governments and stakeholders, particularly in risk or crisis management situations. Recently, blogging or micro-blogging tools, such as Twitter and YouTube, which are very popular social media platforms in the Philippines, have been used to share facts in real-time. They help convey recommendations and warnings very rapidly in real-time.

Rishika (2019) explained the use of disaster media tools in education to help students, teachers, and parents get more useful disaster media to connect with learning groups and other educational systems that make education more convenient and safer. He stressed that disaster media may incorporate social media plugins that enable sharing and interaction, thus saving the lives of students and properties in disaster-affected communities.

According to the NASP School Safety and Crisis Response Committee (2015), disaster media as a social network tool will provide students and institutions with multiple opportunities to boost the teaching and learning process. The schools regard social media as an efficient, quick, and cheap option for communicating with the community, particularly in conveying facts, dispelling rumors, and providing resources that facilitate healthy, adaptive coping. The committee emphasized that schools often

have primary and secondary social or community-mediated platforms (i.e., one very commonly used system). Hence, parents and educators are encouraged to “friend” or “follow” them. These platforms are used by interested schools and education stakeholders so that information and resources are also directly accessible. Ideally, a broad range of crisis resources and information are disseminated to the school’s disaster media personnel, from crisis prevention to crisis recovery. Disaster media can provide schools with accurate and up-to-date information as well as valuable resources. This committee stressed that many parents and guardians are now more likely to use disaster media as a channel of communication websites to find more relevant information. Further, disaster media tools and platforms are relatively easy for most people to use, and they provide an alternative or supplemental way for schools to disseminate crisis-related information quickly. In times of crisis, the school and community can access information, seek connectedness, and find sharable content from school-based disaster media as it alerts or notifies them and all smartphone users quickly and directly. The most common disaster media platforms are Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter. However, preferences change quickly, especially among students and parents.

Recognizing the importance of disaster media as major sources of disaster messages/channels of communication and their effectiveness to DRRM in Albay, this study investigated how these disaster media act as communication channels and as sources of disaster messages or information in times of calamities/typhoons, and how can these be tapped by the two barangays of Tiwi, Albay to save more lives and properties.

Specifically, this study investigated the following questions related to effective communication channels in times of typhoons/disasters: Where do people tend to source their information, or what media channels do they put their trust in? Which of these disaster media can they access more relevant, timely, understandable, and accurate information during calamities or disasters? Moreover, which of these media they perceive as effective in helping them make an informed decision? In addition, this study also tried to determine the communication system or network on which the locality operates during disasters and identify what communication tools are utilized by the system.

Statement of the Problem

This study attempted to answer the following research questions:

1. How do people affected by the disaster or TD Usman in Tiwi, Albay utilize disaster media as communication channels/sources of information, in terms of:
 - community influencers in their localities;
 - disaster media channels utilized by the barangays; including the crisis communication framework or system operating in Tiwi, Albay;
 - communication tools and devices utilized by the barangays; including the crisis communication framework or system operating in Tiwi, Albay; and
 - frequency of use of the disaster media as channels of communication during disasters and TD Usman
2. What are the existing disaster media communication networks in Tiwi, Albay during a disaster or TD Usman?

3. What are the preparations made by the barangays for maintaining communication during a disaster or TD Usman?
4. How effective are the disaster media communication channels used by barangays in making informed decisions about DRRM in Tiwi, Albay in terms of timeliness, accuracy, relevance, and understandability?
5. What issues or challenges have been encountered in utilizing the disaster media channels/sources of information?

Objectives of the Study

This study aimed to determine the available disaster media as communication channels utilized during disasters and identify the most effective sources of information for providing timely, accurate, relevant, and understandable messages or information to the heavily affected community in Tiwi Albay.

Specifically, it aimed to:

- 1) Determine how the disaster media, as communication channels/sources of information, was utilized by the people affected by the disaster or TD Usman (i) community influencers in the local community; (ii) disaster media channels utilized by the barangays including the disaster communication framework or system operating in Tiwi Albay; (iii) communication tools and devices utilized by the barangays including the disaster communication framework or system operating in Tiwi Albay; and (iv) frequency of use of the disaster media as channels of communications during disasters and TD Usman.

- 2) Identify existing disaster media communication networks in Tiwi, Albay during disaster or TD Usman.
- 3) Determine preparations made by the barangays in maintaining communication during a disaster or TD Usman.
- 4) Determine how effective the disaster media communication channels used by barangays in making informed decisions about DRRM in Tiwi, Albay in terms of timeliness, accuracy, relevance; understandability.
- 5) Identify the various issues or challenges encountered by the barangays in using the disaster media channels/sources of information.

Significance of the Study

The study provides an in-depth understanding of the communication dynamics during disasters and serves as a guide for people affected by them.

The outcome of the study will help the responders, government officials, and other stakeholders involved in disaster risk and reduction management come up with an enhanced and appropriate disaster communication plan or communication system policies.

The results of this study will also guide disaster communicators and information officers involved in information dissemination and disaster education in enhancing communication systems and resources for improved DRRM.

The findings of this study will help the teachers in the Department of Education Region V enhance the integration of disaster risk and reduction management concepts in the education curriculum for an effective application. It will also serve as a reference for teachers and learners in the basic education program, especially in the Senior High

School where media and information literacy are expected to be incorporated into the curriculum.

This study may help DOST offices such as PAGASA and PhiVolcs in their mandate to issue accurate, timely, and understandable information on weather forecasts and advisories. The study results will help them identify which communication channel can be effectively tapped to reach their target audience.

The results of this study will also help the local community officials effectively communicate information about the disasters to the affected populace.

This study may serve as reference material for researchers who will conduct further studies on communications and disaster risk and reduction management.

Chapter II

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

This chapter discusses literature and research reviews relevant to the current study, provides a theoretical background in understanding the study, and points out research gaps within the current study. This review of the literature draws from four (4) different research perspectives. First, literature and research that identifies the disaster media as disaster information/sources and their effectiveness for DRRM are highlighted, including various sources of information and their effectiveness as well as timeliness, relevance, and understandability. Second, the literature on the existing disaster media communication networks, the preparations made by the local government to maintain communication/information channels, as well as the issues or challenges encountered by the community are examined. Third, it explores how communication infrastructures and interoperability might adapt to the emerging use of social media for disaster mitigation and control. Finally, the relevance of knowledge management system best practices that will serve as the basis for developing an effective DRRM in Albay is highlighted.

Communication channels for disaster information/sources

Wendling, et, al. (2013) have identified five (5) types of social media, namely:

- i) Social networking media (i.e., Facebook, Myspace) - which brings together a group of people, with a shared common interest;
- ii) Content sharing media (i.e. YouTube, Flickr, etc.) allows anyone to upload content such as videos or pictures and share it with everyone in a restricted community of users;
- iii) Collaborating knowledge sharing media (i.e., Wikis and podcasts) enable participants to ask questions and then wait for

responses coming from different types of users; (iv) Blogging or microblogging tools such as Twitter can be used to share facts, values, emotions, and expectations in real-time, but also convey advice and warnings very quickly, and, (v) Volunteer Technical Community (VTC) which is a social media platform or module created for risk and crisis communication.

These different types of disaster media can complement each other in risk and crisis management, for they can help strengthen coordination between volunteers and emergency services (Wendling, et. al, 2013). These media can also help affected communities conduct situational awareness by identifying images or videos to help create a dialogue between different stakeholders in risk or crisis management situations. The different types of social media can be complementary in risk and crisis management as they can help enhance coordination among volunteers and emergency services.

Social media, one of the communication channels of disaster information/sources, also supports media monitoring of humanitarian responses through technical approaches of crowdsourcing, data mining, reliance on trained volunteers for surveillance, situational awareness, and use of early warning system tools. As a communication tool, social media can provide information and instructions, with real-time alerts and warnings. Further, social media can be used to identify survivors and victims and help find out if family and friends are safe. When combined with a cell phone, social media can help report incidents accurately and requests for help. Utilizing disaster media for risk and crisis communication can help counter inaccurate press coverage or counterbalance rumors and manage reputational effects.

Wendling et al., (2013) also argued that disaster media could be used to encourage foreign and local donations when major catastrophes occur, as well as facilitate the collection of funding and support mechanisms. It is also used to facilitate the supply of support from philanthropies. During an emergency, social media can assist persons who want to help with essentials such as clean water, blankets, and hygiene kits where to bring them, or inform victims of a disaster where they can seek temporary safe shelters for they do not know whom to turn to. It can also facilitate the lessons-learned process and serve as useful material for researchers. The content of social media during a crisis can be rich material for analysis by social scientists to have a better knowledge of risks and crises.

On the other hand, disaster media communication channels like radio, television, newspapers, Facebook, Twitter, and other channels, as articulated by Wendling, et. al. (2013), are valuable communication platforms that assist communities in enhancing disaster preparedness and response efforts as it transmits critical valuable information to many people in the community. Since the late 1990s, disaster media has not only changed the perception of people on disaster risk and crisis management but also the people's expectations toward emergency preparedness and risk mitigation. It is widely used to communicate about risks and crises in the country.

Recently, most people have experienced that disaster media not only helps speed up communication and awareness but also allows real-time communication. With the advent of the Internet and other new media, it will become more manageable as it reduces the number of cell phone calls, press conferences, and other social media platforms from traditional media. With an emerging virus like COVID-19, effective risk communication strategies must be identified to better inform the public and private

sectors, thus mitigating or reducing public health risks. When it comes to risk and crisis communication, disaster media is a useful tool for building trust for it increases transparency and trust in public authorities. In addition, it could also be used to enhance recovery management by sending information on reconstruction and recovery and providing stress management.

In the post-crisis phase, disaster media can be used to send messages about recovery and rebuilding infrastructure such as bridges, routes, and water supply. It can also be used to identify areas that need the most assistance for rehabilitation/recovery. It can also help identify where stress management is most needed in the recovery phase and thus offer tools for managing stress through interactive platforms. Moreover, people use disaster media spontaneously, especially in the post-crisis phase, to increase resilience and solidarity among affected communities.

Lovari and Bowen (2019) conducted a study to determine how disaster media were utilized during a flood disaster, including the gaps between theories and practice. The researchers also elaborated that during the disaster, the communities may adopt the multidisciplinary approach which involves public relations-related activities, social media studies, government/public affairs, and public sector communication, among others.

Boholano et al., (2012) emphasized the complexity of current disasters creates a challenge for crisis communication. This research provided a practical-oriented overview of the communication constraints in complex crises, which has not been provided so far, and the development of the discipline in communication as an integral part of the decision-making in disaster management. The result of the study revealed

that the basic requisite for effective disaster-relief operations and mitigation is the efficient and effective management of information among various stakeholders, particularly during natural and human-induced disasters.

To Moorthy, Guido, and Gill (2018), efficient information exchanges are also a vital part of disaster response and relief operations, particularly during extended droughts, transboundary haze, earthquakes, floods, hurricanes, tsunamis, landslides, volcanic activities, and severe weather which brought havoc and displaced the affected population. The authors also elaborated that the timely provision of information before, during, and after disasters, which always occur suddenly and often of varying severity, poses a major challenge for effective information exchange and coordination.

Along the same vein, Ulvi et al. (2019) explained that social media such as Facebook, Twitter, and Snapchat, or the Internet, in general, are the most prominent social media platforms that create two-way interaction opportunities between organizations, the public, and individuals. When the community fully utilizes social media in tandem with the mass media, it will save more lives and properties. On the other hand, mass media such as newspapers, radio, and television play a pivotal role in disaster dissemination, as they facilitate the one-way spread of information (Sutton, et. al., 2015). It is also used to save more lives by connecting people with ways to overcome adversity in disaster-related events such as floods, storms, and hurricanes (Sutton, et. al., 2015).

Other literature and studies also reported that, during an emergency, people from the affected areas obtained weather information from mass media and social media platforms, which are uniquely different from traditional ones. These channels

of communication can help disseminate targeted information during a crisis. After a natural disaster takes place, infrastructure and access to health services are compromised. A systematic review of literature and studies was commissioned by the World Health Organization (WHO) to integrate Emergency Risk Communication (ERC) best practices into governmental and non-governmental health systems for all public health emergencies. The results of the study serve as valuable inputs in the formulation of the ERC guidelines (Jha, et. al., 2018).

The ERC was identified as one of the most effective ways to communicate with the general public, particularly during and after a disaster/typhoon. Combined with social media, ERC helps predict disaster risks and their severity. In the case of Hurricane Sandy, the use of social media resulted in dramatic increases when traumatic events occurred.

Now that almost everyone in the communities has cell phones, it will keep everyone "in the loop" of much-needed information, particularly when, where, and what to do to prepare in times of disaster or emergency (Ulvi, et al. 2019). These researchers say disaster media allows users to communicate and share messages through social networking. They argued that disaster media is a crucial tool during a natural disaster for it is utilized to educate, relocate, rescue, aid, and provide mental, physical, and emotional support to save people's lives.

Likewise, networks are used to communicate varied topics and can educate people at an exponential rate during natural disaster events (Sutton, et. al., 2015). Through Twitter alone, millions of users interact each day, and during disaster times, the number of interactions and tweets increases. Further, the authors stressed that tweets with valid information and emotional appeal encourage safety and participation

and are the most shared and retweeted. They further reported that tweets regarding natural disasters may somehow inform the public by conveying risk factors, identifying the locations for communities to stay away from, where aid is closely located, including the locations of high exposures, the people who urgently need immediate assistance, and others.

Furthermore, mass media like newspapers, radio, and television also play a vital role in disaster communication, particularly in facilitating one-way information dissemination. On the other hand, social media such as Facebook, Twitter, and the Internet, in general, have created two-way interaction opportunities among organizations, the public, and individuals.

Tracy (2022) reported that media platforms have gained tremendous momentum in this 21st century and can now change how people interact, including how companies do business. Like other media platforms displaying essential and beneficial information, Facebook now surpasses rivals Twitter Inc. (renamed to X) and LinkedIn Corporation in users and revenue (Tracy, 2022). The times are changing, education and technology are constantly evolving, and public health professionals must adapt to the generations to reach out to everyone. However, public health professionals and emergency response teams utilize social media to help educate, relocate, rescue, and provide mental, physical, and emotional support, with the end-in goal of saving the lives of the users of the networks affected by disasters/typhoons.

The study by Tracy (2022) covered more areas than the present study. However, both addressed the need for a more effective disaster communication network. Although the current study did not discuss inter-agency cooperation, they are complementary since the present study identified the communication channels during

a disaster. Tracy (2022), indeed, provided an effective platform for disaster communication, which could be used to make further implications in the current study.

Information Technology and Disaster Management

Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) as explained by the International Telecommunication Union [ITU], (n.d.) play a significant role, especially in terms of disaster prevention, mitigation response, mitigation, and recovery efforts. ITU (n.d.) elaborated that timely, predictable, and effective information is deemed necessary for government agencies and other humanitarian actors for decision-making processes related to rescue operations. ICTs for Disaster Management as articulated by ITU, (n.d.) follows four (4) principles, namely: multi-hazard, multi-technology, multi-phased, and multi-stakeholder.

Today, information technology is required because it plays a critical role in disaster management phases. Understanding the IT role would somehow strengthen disaster risk management and mitigation measures, thereby saving more lives and properties and speeding recovery during catastrophes. For successful disaster management, however, the data must be obtained and arranged in a very logical and timely manner. From the local government's perspective, the essential roles of data systems, (i.e., information record, exchange, and process), are critical in effective disaster management. Information records and exchange are the initial functions of data systems before a disaster, while information process and exchange become core to disaster relief operations (ITU, n.d).

Moreover, understanding, organizing, and maintaining effective communication during a disaster are vital for the execution of rescue operations and therefore the

demand for ICT services has increased, especially after the disaster. It is believed that if ICTU services are uprooted as a pre-disaster network system, it will then cause severe network traffic congestion which would eventually result in physical damage to ICT equipment and emergency ICT networks. Further, it also proposes an architecture design integrating the current network infrastructure with the reinforcement of layers-based techniques and cloud processing concepts. The integration and reinforcement allow the ICT services to be developed and launched within an affordable short period (ITU, n.d.).

Furthermore, Kamran, et al. (2019) explained that communication in an ongoing disaster is maintained through the effective implementation of the three-tier fortification of the overall network design, and some researchers believe that it minimizes the physical and logical redundancy of resilient and versatile ICT resources. As cloud processing works as a parallel reinforced infrastructure, the network design will give new hope to contemplate cloud computing services for effectiveness and better dependability on the architecture to save ICT and humanitarian networks at the time of disaster.

Haddow and Haddow, (2014), in their book titled "Disaster Communications in a Changing Media World", underscored that communication is key to the success of disaster mitigation, preparedness, response, and recovery. They also stressed that accurate information disseminated to the public, elected officials and community leaders, and other media platforms would somehow reduce disaster risk, save lives and property, and hasten recovery. They also provided valuable information, particularly in navigating the priorities in an age of evolving media. The emergence of the latest media like the Internet, email, blogs, text messaging, telephone, and photos, and the increasing influence of first informers are redefining the roles of social media.

Today, the tools and rules of communication are evolving, and thus, disaster communication must also evolve to accommodate these changes and exploit the available opportunities.

Haddow and Haddow, (2014) also brighten the trail to effective disaster communication, including the need for transparency, increased accessibility, trustworthiness, reliability, and partnerships with the media. The authors present various case studies from recent disasters, including the 2011 tsunami in Japan, Hurricane Sandy in 2012, and the Boston Marathon bombings in 2013 which referenced the various disaster media utilized by other countries. These demonstrate the effective use of various social media platforms like blogs, text messages, and mobile phone cameras, which can also be used as government channels and traditional media during a crisis.

Likewise, Haddow and Haddow (2014) also touched on a wider range of topics than what the present study covered. They provide background material for understanding and appreciating the role of disaster communication in today's world. The authors enrich the mind to grasp the importance of digital technology and innovation in making disaster management more relevant to the requirements of the time.

Yi and Kuri (2016) argued that in this modern society, where massive amounts of information are exchanged instantaneously, the topics of discussion would shift rapidly due to ICT. With the advent of ICT, most people have now turned to sharing information to foster a sense of membership in their society, and the trend of internet communication exists among many types of people or groups. During and after the disasters, social networking services (SNS) were reported as a considerably effective

method for sharing/exchanging information about the disaster and its significance. It is widely used in confirming the whereabouts of family members and friends, locating shelters, finding relief, food, and goods rationing. It is widely used in terms of confirming family members' and friends' whereabouts, locating shelters, and finding relief, food, and goods rationing areas. This has been proven during the 2011 Great East Japan earthquake and Tsunami and the 2013 Typhoon Haiyan (local name, Yolanda) in the Philippines.

SNS is not only used to share/exchange information, it also seeks and provides information by communicating with the public through government agencies using social media channels. Therefore, the development and adoption of communications in virtual spaces can be very effective for decision-makers, especially in providing emergencies

Crisis Communication Attributes and Channels

In the book entitled "Societies in the Information Age: A Critical Perspective", Flor (2009) explains that information and communication are integral to our environment. The author reminds us that we are now in the information age, thus, whether we like it or not, whether we adapt or not, we need to become the primary asset for change and development, greater than the physical and mechanical resources. Hence, full control can be achieved through an effective communication channel. To achieve full control, people must use information as the primary resource and communication. It will serve as the tool for interventions, improvements, or alterations to a better quality of life.

Flor (2009) also emphasized that survival is part of everyday life in this era of the Information Age. Thus, people need, more than ever, to have information, and

must communicate to control and survive. The need for communication is required in communities more exposed and vulnerable to calamities and disasters. There have been studies highlighting that the need for information and communication also increases when disaster strikes. Disaster-affected communities have shown such need and stressed that information plays an important psychological role in alleviating human suffering (Lynch, 2010). Flor (2009) calls this in his book "a mad scramble for communication resources" when the rate and amount of communication have increased in an almost mind-boggling manner through the merging of computer, broadcast, cables, and telephone technology, collectively called ICT. This was true at the turn of the Information Age as it is apparent when a disaster strikes in a community. People are also dynamic in the communication space, accessing multiple and overlapping information channels. When a crisis is unfolding, people no longer wait for an official statement from government actors; rather, they turn to the news media, go to Twitter or Facebook, and log onto forums and blogs, because they expect information, and they can get it quickly from various sources (3RG Special Report, 2009).

Taking the tsunami tragedy in Japan and Typhoon Haiyan in the Philippines as examples, the study emphasized the importance of mass media in disaster operations. One of the lessons learned during emergencies and disasters is to fulfill the need to send and receive information. Every time a disaster happens, people will always look for information from available sources and utilize whatever means of communication there is. At present, there are different kinds of media utilized as channels of communication. Media is the plural form of medium, which can include anything from printed paper to digital data, and encompasses news, educational content, and numerous other forms of information (Technopedia, 2020).

The technology used to handle these media converging with other technologies and using common transmission lines capable of carrying very diverse data and communication types and formats are ICT. According to Mahse (2010), ICT comprises computer hardware and software applications, including mobile phones, computers, network hardware, internet, telecommunication systems, and so on, as well as various related services and applications. ICT is now being utilized in almost all government offices in the Philippines. Social media, on the other hand, is a computer-based technology that facilitates the sharing of ideas, thoughts, and information through the building of virtual networks and communities. By design, social media is internet-based and gives users quick electronic communication of content (Investopedia, 2020). Communication Media represents any conglomeration of the common types of mass media: print, broadcast, mobile phones for short message service or text messaging, and social media.

Crisis communication, as part of the communication media, is a challenging endeavor (Comfort, Ko, and Zagorecki (2004); Ehnis and Bunker (2012); Paton, Johnston, Mamula-Seadon, and Kenney, (2014). Thus, when disaster happens, people need to respond and when they respond, it requires timely, consistent, and accurate information that informs how they might meet their needs. Furthermore, the circumstances and the needs people experience, require competencies to meet these needs, which vary from place to place, and from group to group. The purposes of disaster and crisis communication are to prevent panic, promote appropriate health behaviors, coordinate immediate and appropriate response and mitigation measures among stakeholders, advocate for affected populations, and mobilize resources (Medfors-Davis & Kapur, 2014).

Suleyman et al. (2009) opined that there are life-saving values when information and communication processes are timely and responsive. This was supported by the actual data gathered in the aftermath of the 1999 earthquakes in Turkey. It was reported that difficulties in accessing and exchanging timely and accurate disaster-relevant information inhibited coordination just like the Marmara response. Increasing communication functions may improve coordination and search-and-rescue activities and this happened during the Duzce response. The Marmara earthquake is reported to be the most devastating earthquake in the history of modern Turkey.

According to the Hurriyet Daily News (2019) report, the Marmara earthquake killed about 17,000 people in August 1999. The Duzce earthquake, on the other hand, reported about 1000 fatalities in November 1999 (Muhammed and Ergin, 2000). Moreover, timeliness and accuracy of information as evidenced in the studies conducted have been shown to contribute to greater response and effectiveness of disaster management in the localities.

The existence of an advanced ICT paves the way for more complex, dynamic, two-way information sharing to and from multiple directions and varied sources. ICT as the key driver of the trend is the technology that provides access to information via the internet, wireless networks, cell phones, and other communications media.

Social media is the communication service within ICT. This employs interactive digital communication with user-generated content and has the potential to manipulate or influence audiences. While traditional media such as television, newspapers, and radio continue to play a prominent role in daily life and certainly during disasters, these media represent the old communication paradigm, one that is characterized by one-

way information sharing (Fraustino, Brooke, and Yan, 2012). With the accessibility of ICT in today's world, nothing could be made impossible if it is recognized and integrated into disaster management. As a tool for advanced information dissemination, social media can encourage the receiver to take some actions to avoid a possible threat or harmful effect and thus, create a rational understanding of the risks (Seeger, Sellnow, Timothy, Ulmer, 2016). It was also reported that new information technologies have a special beneficial role to play in creating community resilience by developing social capital, including the creation of collective intelligence via coordinative responses, and the initiation of discussions about risks and management and mitigation measures. Olson (2019) reported that more and more communities are indeed accessing quad media like ICT, social media, and traditional media.

However, the traditional media is still popular in communities where ICTs have not yet been introduced or the potential has not yet been fully utilized. This is perceived to exist particularly in developing countries and in communities that are still geographically or socially detached from the full influence of the Information Age. The gap, called the digital divide, can deprive lower-income segments of the population from receiving important information during times of crisis (Abdulraman, 2018). Even with the development and utilization of ICT and social media, other findings suggest that traditional media is still the most important source of information. In a study involving higher education students taking up Environmental Disaster Management at the University of Dodoma in Tanzania, it was found that most of the students are using mobile phones and accessing social media but are limited by the costs of data access, and thus, they shared disaster information moderately and still rely on oral and traditional media.

In Haiti, it was noted that text messaging is the primary means of remote communication, surpassing email, and traditional mail and often (for pricing and reliability) actual phone calls. However, it was also implied that the shared commitment of people physically remote from each other but working together in an online collaborative environment built a strong community that serves as the key step in the emergency response processes, and not because of the means of communication used. It went on to say that, technically and socially, SMS is more of a peer-to-peer communication service than a broadcast medium. The power lies in distributed systems, not channeling all communication through one centrally controlled service (Meier, and Munro, 2010).

Disasters could strike everywhere at any given place and time. However, the United Nations Economic and Social Commission for Asia and the Pacific (ESCAP) affirms that, in 2015, Asia-Pacific continued to be the world's most disaster-prone region. 160 disasters were reported, accounting for 47 percent of the world's 344 disasters. Its first large-scale catastrophic disaster reportedly killed over 16,000 people, more than tripling the number of typhoon/disaster-related deaths since 2014. South Asia accounted for a staggering 64 percent of total global fatalities wherein the majority was attributed to the 7.6 magnitude earthquake that struck Nepal in April which reported 8,790 fatalities. Asia and the Pacific incurred more than USD 45.1 billion in economic damage in 2015 and even higher indirect losses (United Nations Economic and Social Commission for Asia and the Pacific, 2016). The Region is known to sit within the very active Pacific Ring of Fire, the main factor triggering calamities in the localities surrounding it. Given this report, the Region could be demanding more utilization of information transfers and communication for disaster management coherent with the potential benefits the Information Age presents.

The Philippine Government, International Non-governmental Organizations (INGOs) and local NGOs are all making attempts to address the impact of disasters and climate change at various levels in the Philippines. The country has also implemented disaster risk reduction (DRR) planning and activities programs and projects geared towards risk reduction and management through the Office of Civil Defense (OCD) National Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Council (NDRRMC). Similarly, the Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD), the agency responsible for leading immediate disaster relief efforts, is always there to help the communities affected by the disaster. Awareness of disaster risk reduction in the Philippines has increased, but proper integration with climate change adaptation and sustainable development policies can be improved. Disaster risk reduction management and climate change adaptation have been integrated into various plans and frameworks. However, multiple plans can be overwhelming for local government units. With Typhoon Haiyan, the province of Albay has learned many things from the risk management report which is believed to be the essential component for the specific typhoon/disaster warnings for the potential storm impacts (relief.web.int., 2017).

In a case study of Typhoon Haiyan and Typhoon Hagupit, which battered the Visayas Region and neighboring provinces of Luzon and Mindanao, it was mentioned that television and radio ranked as the best information sources in the days leading up to the onset of the typhoons. However, post-typhoon communication sources shifted from the traditional media to personal communication with local government officials who have access to ICT and thus, can relay messages through SMS, and verbal communications. For both typhoons, a clear shift was observed in the information sources used before and after the typhoons. Many of those who previously turned to

television and radio for typhoon warnings before landfall began relying on local officials, families, and friends for relief information after the typhoon (Girard, 2016).

A recent tropical depression placed the Region in another climactic event that poses a challenge to the established DRRM protocols of the region. TD USMAN entered the Philippine Area of Responsibility (PAR) on December 25, 2018. The typhoon made landfall in Borongan, Eastern Samar on December 29, 2018 (DAWD, 2014). It has affected four regions, CALABARZON, MIMAROPA, Bicol, and Region VIII. Four provinces of the Bicol Region, namely Albay, Camarines Norte, Camarines Sur, and Sorsogon were affected.

TD Usman had a casualty count of 126 deaths, 60 injured, and 26 missing. Of the 126 deaths, 105 came from Bicol. Mahar Lagmay, a disaster scientist, noted that the impact was attributed to wrong forecasts, late warnings, and a lack of hazard awareness (Conde, 2019). Lagmay's statement PAGASA Administrator Vicente Malano refuted Lagmay's statement, saying the weather forecasters "sufficiently warned" that the "24-hour accumulated rainfall of moderate to heavy could trigger massive flooding and landslides and that they have provided "localized rainfall and thunderstorm warning in near-real time" through its Southern Luzon Pagasa Regional Services Division (SLPRSD) (Marquez, 2019). TD Usman is a disastrous event in the most recent time that can be a good case for assessment, whether communication and utilization of whatever media available for disaster messages dissemination has something to do with the unfortunate turn of events in the affected communities in the Bicol Region.

Earlier studies have affirmed that communication or information exchange during disasters is critical in disaster management and response efforts. The

attributes or the quality of information are also important as individuals and communities need to assess and make informed decisions, actions, and responses. McKinney et. al. (2002) identified five dimensions for information quality: relevance, timeliness, reliability, scope, and perceived usefulness (Oke, Adeynika, & Oluseyi, 2018) while Chiu et al. (2006) determine six: relevance, ease of understanding, accuracy, completeness,

reliability, and timeliness (Chiu, Hsu, and Wang, 2006). Meanwhile, Yong, et al. (2010) considered information quality in terms of reliability, accuracy, timeliness, and relevance.

Yong, et al. (2012) study on Information Exchange in Virtual Communities under extreme disaster conditions yielded useful and encouraging results along with measures of information quality in terms of reliability, accuracy, timeliness, and relevance, the authors recommended further research that may include other dimensions for information quality, such as completeness and ease of understanding.

The studies of Suleyman, Sherik, Corbacioglu, and Sitki (2009) highlight timeliness and accuracy as important characteristics of disaster information to ensure effectiveness.

While previous studies discussed the importance and manner of utilizing various, identified communication channels during emergencies and disasters in different localities, there is a need to determine how disaster media can help the communities mitigate disaster/typhoon risk. Hence, this proposed study will examine how the Philippines, a developing country, utilizes and favors communication channels and recognizes their effectiveness not only as to accuracy, timeliness, and relevance

but also as to understandability or ease of understanding of the information or messages relayed.

The study of Trevor (2016) is a response to failed attempts to inform the public of impending disaster risks, despite the information being available. The study was focused on discovering the factors that can improve the communication of disaster response information, highlighting the "sender" of the information.

The sender includes the source and any intermediaries between the source and the final receivers (public individuals) rather than the receiver of the information.

One of the studied assumptions was verified by comparing the thematic analyses with the survey results. It was confirmed there is a wealth of valuable information available online that fails to help disaster-affected communities. However, the information never reaches them, or the information that does reach the public or the intended user is too technical and thus cannot be fully understood by the public or the end user. The idea is that by differentiating the intermediaries and channels through which the information would flow, the potential source could optimize the form and content of their message and recommend a goal for further research to discover more sources and ways to inform the public. Expanding the variety of the disaster communication system will make it more resilient to the external shocks associated with disasters (Trevor, 2016). This study will then explore the idea by focusing on the receiver of the information to discover what the preferred channels are and what the perceived challenges or barriers in crisis communication.

Effective Communication Channels and Tools for DRMM

One of the most vulnerable regions in the Philippines constantly facing disasters is the Bicol Region. Strong typhoons, volcanic eruptions, flash floods, strong

winds, tsunamis, and drought exacerbated by climate change regularly affect its provinces every year. This has prompted the local government units of the region to implement protocols and improve DRRM efforts. Along with this initiative, many reports and studies have been reviewed and scrutinized by this researcher to better understand the concepts and effective delivery of services in times of disasters/typhoons. There are also several pieces of literature mentioning the role of communications during disasters although the focus was not on this aspect. Other local studies exploring DRRM have mentioned communication tools and channels as factors affecting effective preparation, mitigation, intervention, and relief efforts.

A study looking at the DRRM capability of a local government unit in a municipality of Albay Province identified the means used to communicate disaster warnings by the local DRRM council as verbal (by word of mouth), use of cell phones, use of two-way radio transmitter, through public address system, via transistor radio, via the internet, the church bell, and another channel such as alarm system of siren blasts. While the use of cell phones tops the survey, it did not identify which of these are effective means of communication during disasters (Boholano, 2013).

Another study assessing the practices of identified state universities and colleges in the Bicol Region recognized the communications quad channel as one of the outcomes regarded as an important part of disaster preparedness. Barrameda (2013) has mentioned that the commonly utilized information tools and channels are radio and telephones, social networks, and cellular phones. Oke, Adeynika, and Oluseyi (2018) have also presented the results of their study in terms of the extent of how disaster awareness is communicated and its effect on rural dwellers in Central Nigeria but have not elaborated on the preference and affectivity of the communication channels.

These local studies may have mentioned the types of communication channels utilized during disasters or emergencies but did not cover how effective they were in providing valuable information necessary to support or carry out disaster management and responses.

Various literature reviewed for this present study has pointed out that disaster is a serious disruption to the functioning of a community that exceeds its capacity to cope with its resources. Thus, communication in disasters aims to prevent and mitigate harm from disasters, prepare the population before a disaster, disseminate information during disasters, and aid subsequent recovery. These were among the findings in the systematic review conducted by Bradley et. al (2014) whose aim was to identify, appraise, and synthesize the findings of studies on the effects of risk communication interventions during the four stages of the disaster cycle. This reviewed study provides an idea of how research in the field of disaster management has been done in different parts of the world. It is a modest attempt to participate in the mission of analyzing the field of disaster management, with a focus on disaster communication.

In the international scene, Shittu, Parker, and Mock (2018) shared that in times of emergency, private organizations and public authorities must coordinate in real time to create an effective disaster response. This is indeed true in their research, which examines how to engage with interagency communication and relief organizations and communities in the event of a disaster to develop effective strategies and interventions. Conversely, if coordination is lacking, coordination will fail, creating more chaos, which happened with Hurricane Katrina and the earthquake in Haiti (Shittu et al., 2018). To generate evidence-based and data-driven findings, the researchers developed two (2) cases that best illustrate how to utilize existing technologies and information flows to facilitate DRRM.

The study also reports that a lack of effective information flow between DRRMs often results in poor operational performance. Therefore, when disaster strikes, it is imperative to develop policies to mitigate the collapse of communication infrastructure (Sellnow et al. 2002 in Shittu et al., 2018). Moreover, interesting findings also revealed that Internet and mobile computing tools have created a space for non-traditional volunteers and organizations, which according to the researchers had immediately become the agents/actors in an emergent ephemeral response network for it provides cognitive capital and resources on a global scale (Shittu et al., 2018). The researchers also reported that during the Haiti earthquake, text messages came online too late to be used as 911 types of tools because most of the information received from internet sources came from foreign sources. The only information obtained in the country is related to basic needs such as food and water. The communication channels for hurricanes and earthquakes are reported to be completely different because the underlying issue for successful rescue operations, namely communication resilience, is invariant to disaster type according to the study.

In the case of Haiti, the findings show how telecommunications infrastructure, especially social networking tools, can recover quickly after a disaster and combine with new technologies due to efficient communication/information transfer. Shittu, et al (2018) report that information is affected by the need for relief as it is transmitted; but the outcome of subsequent response efforts is largely unknown, creating a feedback gap between communication channels. The researchers also revealed that cellular networks became more resilient to the catastrophe between Katrina and Haiti which is a product of technological evolution with the emergence of more integrated cell phone and internet services in the affected country. Likewise, the internet and mobile computing tools have reportedly created a space for non-traditional volunteers

and organizations to eventually become important players in the emerging ephemeral response network. It mobilizes cognitive capital and resources globally, across organizational boundaries, and the conflict remains a significant barrier to an effective DRRM model (Shittu et al., 2018).

The Philippines, one of the vulnerable and disaster-prone countries, may address the challenges posed by threatening disasters in each city through DRRM communication initiatives just like the strategies and interventions mentioned by Shittu et al., (2018). Becodo (2015) analyzed governance communications currently available for disaster risk reduction and management (DRRM) in disaster-prone communities in Iloilo Province, Philippines. This study provides the cultural context by focusing on the local government units of the country. However, the communication channel varies because of the size and status of the LGU used as the locale. Becodo (2015) revealed that DRRM activities conducted in the selected municipalities did not contribute to the disaster preparedness of the community stakeholders. They overlooked their city's communication protocol as one of the factors that might help improve people's knowledge and participation in DRRM, which might help in disaster preparedness and awareness.

In times of emergency, private organizations, as well as public authorities, must coordinate in real time to create an effective DRRM. However, without coordination, there will be failures and possibly more chaos, as happened with Hurricane Katrina and the earthquake in Haiti (Shittu, Parker, and Mock, 2018). This is true in the study of Shittu et al. (2018), which examined how to engage with interagency communication and relief organizations and communities to develop effective strategies and interventions in the event of a disaster.

In addition to improving preparedness and raising public awareness of risks and crises. Wendling et al. (2013) also elaborated that social media in disaster risk management can also be leveraged. Social media can represent one more channel for emergency services to convey an alert and warning. This is the case with natural disasters such as storms like TD Usman. Social media such as blogs can provide information and instructions, including advice, by posting information such as emergency phone numbers, locations of hospitals that need blood donations, evacuation routes, and more. Likewise, social media can be used to mobilize volunteers during and after a crisis, for it can be used to signal willingness to help in an emergency. Additionally, it can improve disaster response by mobilizing online volunteers to deliver information and provide emergency services.

A high-level "elite" interview with the state's top emergency managers about their social media policies, practices, and use in both media relations and citizen communication was conducted by the researcher. Based on the results of the interview, strategies, and communication models were implemented, including the challenges and barriers to effective adoption of these platforms. The ethical implications of the use of social media during natural disasters were also explored. To improve disaster communication via social media, the researchers recommended providing resources, evaluation, symmetry, and utilization of ethical communication to suppress rumors or misinformation during a disaster and assigning dedicated staff to oversee the DRRM activities. In addition, accurate information is needed in disaster preparedness so that the frontliners can plan and effectively implement disaster response operations. It can also serve as a venue for information dissemination in disaster situations.

The Albay DRRM Communication Framework

The huge impact of the Super-typhoon Reming experience prompted the prioritization of a typhoon communication preparedness program for the province of Albay, including the designing of a communication framework. The communication framework of Albay became the model for the Republic Act 10121, otherwise known as the Philippine Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) Act. RA 10121 mandates strengthening disaster management in the Philippines. It aims to develop a framework and roll out resources that will enable the national government, the local government units, and other stakeholders to build resilient communities that can survive disasters. It also emphasizes strengthening the capabilities of local governments and the importance of local communities. Aside from articulating the funding, resources, and response and mitigation protocols, it also developed a communication protocol that must be implemented down to the community or barangay level (Sarmienta, 2016). The communication protocol operates with information coming from PAGASA and PHIVOLCS as the only credible sources of information for weather disturbances and advisories. Then, the information is relayed to the NDRRMC and will be transmitted to RDRRMC, PDRRMC, CDRRMC to BDRRMC (Daep, C. Personal Communication).

The framework, as described by Daep, utilizes gadgets and communication tools such as mobile phones, VHF radio, social media, radio broadcasts, and sound alarm systems. They have also tapped the potential of ICT in employing the SMART Info Board where information via SMS can be relayed simultaneously to most target recipients. The SMART Info Board is part of SMART's corporate social responsibility in Albay. They also have the GPS-based Provincial Information Network on Disaster Occurrence and Threats (PINDOT) in the framework. PINDOT sends warning

communications and facilitates the incident command system during and after calamities. The same communication tools are utilized at the barangay level. Face-to-face communication with the residents is employed when necessary.

Synthesis

In summary, the foregoing literature and studies provide an empirical basis for designing and evaluating the disaster media as the primary source of information/messages used by communities during disasters/typhoons and their effectiveness to DRRM. The reviewed literature discussed a much larger concept than what the current study adheres to, but both the literature and the current study dealt with disaster communications.

The reviewed studies also suggest that information technology should be used in disaster communication, which is what aspiring local government units would like to do in the future, given that funding for disaster risk reduction and management would be provided. It underscored that accurate information is needed in disaster preparedness and could be disseminated to the general public, elected officials, community leaders, and the media to reduce risk, save lives and property, and speed up recovery so that the frontliners can plan and effectively implement disaster response operations. Indeed, communications are key to the success of disaster mitigation, preparedness, response, and recovery.

However, to respond effectively, people need information about events, support resources, actions, and the like as well as the ability to interpret and use the available information to respond to a variety of emergency disaster consequences and needs. Likewise, effective information exchange is an essential part of disaster response and relief operations. The reviewed literature and studies have also pointed out that new

information technologies have a special beneficial role, particularly in creating community resilience by developing social capital and creating collective intelligence. In addition, it also guides the researcher in coordinating effective communication responses, and how to initiate discussions within the affected communities about risk-related issues and concerns as well as mitigation and control measures. Communication or information exchange during disasters is critical for disaster management and response.

Moreover, the attributes or the quality of information are also important because individuals and communities need them to assess and make informed decisions, actions, and responses. In addition to traditional media, more communities are accessing ICT and social media. Also, information exchange in virtual communities under extreme disaster conditions yielded useful and encouraging results together with measures of information quality such as reliability, accuracy, timeliness, and relevance. The authors recommended further research that may include other dimensions for information quality, such as completeness and ease of understanding. Timeliness and accuracy are also important characteristics of disaster information to ensure effectiveness.

Recently, various media platforms have been used as venues for disseminating information in disaster situations. However, other researchers have warned that in the event of a disaster, people with disabilities cannot access increasingly complex and overlapping digital communication platforms, which could make already life-threatening situations even more dangerous. The complexity of current disasters creates a challenge for crisis communication. Thus, social media is now the most efficient method of delivering emergency response messages in a modern urban crisis scenario. In the aftermath of an event, the results of the literature reviewed will provide

valuable spatially relevant information that is often difficult to pin down in the disaster media during and after a disaster or calamity. In this era of the information age, more than ever, people need to have information and must communicate to control and survive. Massive amounts of information are exchanged in real time, and topics change rapidly. Moreover, people desire and share information to foster a sense of membership in their societies, and the trend of Internet communication is present in many types of groups.

Some of the reviewed literature and studies have pointed out that disaster-affected communities play an important psychological role that can alleviate human suffering. Thus, the information and competencies required vary from place to place, from group to group to meet the needs of the affected communities. Difficulties in obtaining and exchanging timely and accurate disaster-related information also hinder coordinated responses, while increased communications capabilities may improve coordination as well as search and rescue activities.

Finally, a review of relevant literature and studies also provides information on the research topics that can be explored by future researchers on disaster media as a channel of communication during typhoons and disasters. However, there is no existing literature and studies related to Tiwi Albay's effective and efficient disaster communications channel of information, particularly in barangays Maynonong and Mayong, where the current study was undertaken.

Theoretical Framework

This study adopts the theory of the Social Mediated Crisis Communication (SMCC) model developed by Liu et al. (2012). This model is useful for emergency communication efforts, especially in identifying at-risk groups and how best to reach

them to save more lives and property. It was developed to provide evidence-based guidelines to help crisis communicators, particularly those affected by typhoons/disasters. The SMCC model helps us decide when and how to respond to influential social media, while also acknowledging the influence of social media and traditional media as well as offline word-of-mouth communication.

According to Cheng (2019), the model (Figure 2) has been extensively tested in several countries, including the United States, using different research methods, including experimental studies and/or quantitative and qualitative studies.

Figure 2.

The social-mediated crisis communication (SMCC) model.

Some of the research questions were related to the investigations on: 1) how crisis information forms, sources of information, crisis type, and history which might influence the public (e.g., influential social media content creators, followers, and inactive) disasters/typhoons' crisis responses; 2) how types of organizations (i.e., local government units, private organizations NGOs) may respond to publics effectively by adopting different crisis communication strategies during disasters/typhoons.

The SMCC framework highlights the importance of integrating social media into the media mix for crisis communication and issues management (Liu, Jin, Austin, & Janoske, 2012). This theory supports the communication model in the context of a communication crisis, as many “publics” or audiences exist in the world of social media, including influencers, followers, and inactive members. Austin, Liu & Jin (2012) further explain in Cheng (2019) that the essence of the current model lies in the direct and indirect dissemination of information across and between traditional and social media.

The SMCC model identifies three key publics who seek, produce, or share information before, during, and after crises. They are the influential social media creators, social media followers, and social media interactives. Influential social media creators develop and post-crisis information online. The social media followers consume this information from social media creators and also share this information both online and offline. The social media inactives do not participate actively in social media, but receive this crisis information via other channels, including traditional media and word-of-mouth communication, from social media followers, creators, or other inactives (Austin and Yan, 2016). The solid arrows represent direct relationships in the flow of information, while dotted arrows represent indirect relationships. For example, social media inactives have an indirect relationship with social media, receiving information indirectly from followers and creators. Arrows also indicate a two-way, reciprocal flow of information. For example, social media and traditional media directly inform one another’s crisis coverage, with traditional media utilizing information from social media in news development, and vice versa. The model also highlights three main forms of crisis communication, namely social media, traditional media, and word-of-mouth communication. The organization responds to an issue/crisis and the key

publics is situated within a gray box in the model to represent the ubiquitous nature of online word-of-mouth communication among the organization and social media creators, followers, and inactives. Social media, which may include information from influential, social media creators, or the organization, has a direct relationship with key publics, the organization, and traditional media, while traditional media has a direct relationship with social media, the key public, and the organization.

Essential to this model is the direct and indirect dissemination of information across social media, as well as between traditional and social media (Austin, Liu & Jin, 2012). This model is useful for communication efforts in emergencies when defining the at-risk population and how best to reach them. In a world increasingly connected via social media, information exchanged on this platform during emergencies has the potential to engage with multiple types of public audiences. Although inactive members may be connected to social media indirectly, through other members or traditional media, these individuals may require different messaging channels than influential followers. This theory provides a model that identifies the characteristics of audiences that can help refine communication strategies and components.

While previous studies discussed the importance and manner of utilizing various, identified communication channels during emergencies and disasters in different localities, there is a need to determine how disaster media can help the communities mitigate disaster/typhoon risk. Hence, this proposed study will examine how the Philippines, a developing country, utilizes and favors communication channels and recognizes their effectiveness not only as to accuracy, timeliness, and relevance but also as to understandability or ease of understanding of the information or messages relayed.

Conceptual Framework

In the information age, the world is not only engaged in traditional and non-traditional media but is also increasingly connected via social media where information exchanged on this platform during emergencies has the potential to engage with multiple audiences. Although the ones classified as inactive members may not be directly connected to social media, they may access information through other members or from traditional media who have access to social media; they may also require different messaging channels other than influencers and followers. With the SMCC's components: information form (traditional media, social media, and word-of-mouth), and source (third party), the model can identify the characteristics of audiences that can help refine applicable communication strategies deemed effective during crises or disasters. This theory describes the relationship between organizations, online and offline publics, social media, traditional media, and word-of-mouth communication before, during, and after disaster crises (Austin, Fraustino, Jin, & Liu, 2017 in Cheng, 2019). Figure 3 adopts the SMCC Model in Tiwi, Albay.

Figure 3.

The SMCC Model as Conceptual Framework in Disaster Communication in Tiwi, Albay.

Figure 3 describes the relationship between the following core concepts: the organization, key publics, social media, traditional media, and online word-of-mouth communication before, during, and after crises, and the form and flow of information; each carrying the message that would require the criteria of being timely, accurate, understandable, and relevant to be considered effective in sharing or disseminating the information or messages. Effective communication during disasters that considers these qualities leads to effective disaster risk and reduction management. However, there are situations where challenges and setbacks, identified as noise in the communication process, interfere with the delivery of the information diminishing its quality and contributing to an ineffective DRRM and misinformed public.

It illustrates the dynamics of communication with disaster media and how community influencers and organizations interact to deliver and consume information in times of disaster. It also defines the flow of disaster information and relationships between different types of media, online and offline communication, as well as the organization and community influencers during disasters in the study. The organizations in this study are the local government units of Barangay Mayong and Maynonong. The key publics of this study are the community influencers such as neighbors, kumare/kumpare, local officials, and religious leaders. The forms of communication in the study are the traditional media, comprising newspaper, television, radio, and offline word of mouth. The flow of information, such as seeking information, processing, and sharing, can be direct or indirect as shown in the model. Organizational structure, factors impinging on the disaster, and the messaging strategy employed are also considered, much like in the SMCC model.

Paton and Irons (2016) claimed that disasters can create an urgent need for people to house novel emergent problems. They suggested that for it to be more efficient and effective, people need information about the event, support resources, actions, and other related matters. They recommended that people also use their skills and abilities to interpret and use available information, as well as handle diverse, emergent hazard consequences and demands over time. The diversity has rendered top-down, homogeneous approaches to the disaster, which made disaster communication ineffective (Paton and Irons, 2016).

The above-mentioned literature somehow provided a background to this study as it attempted to examine whether a social media-based communication strategy, using Facebook, represents a simpler way of accommodating this diversity (e.g., event impacts, geographical, demographic, social), meeting the knowledge needs have affected populations and enhancing the standard of disaster communication. The data was obtained using an open-ended questionnaire gathered from 479 people who used a Facebook page (Tassie Fires – we can Help) specifically in terms of developing a channel of communications to help in the response and recovery of the 2011 Tasmanian wildfire/bushfire disaster. It also includes the accounts of people's experience of the event and their engagement with the Facebook page would serve as the basis for coming up with an effective DRRM strategy in Albay.

Chapter III

METHODOLOGY

This chapter discusses the research methodology, research locale, the determination of sample size, the respondents, the data-gathering instruments, statistics, and statistical analysis used in the study.

Research Methodologies

This research adopted the mixed method developed by Creswell (2014) using explanatory sequential design. The technique involves collecting quantitative and qualitative data, integrating these two forms of data, and using distinct designs that may include philosophical assumptions and theoretical frameworks related to disaster media. The quantitative data were gathered first and was reinforced by the collection of the qualitative data. Creswell (2014) emphasized that the combination of quantitative and qualitative approaches provides a more complete understanding of the research problem. The goal of this study is to determine the available disaster media communication channels utilized as sources of disaster information and their effectiveness against the quality or criteria of the disaster information/messages for disaster communication in DRRM.

The theoretical model was developed as a guide in determining the conditions surrounding the barangay residents, including the nature of the situation, and to explore the causes of specific phenomena during the occurrence of TD Usman and its impact in the studied barangays in Tiwi, Albay.

To determine the various disaster media of disaster messages and their effectiveness on DRRM, the researcher chose participants from the two selected barangays in Tiwi Albay. The following selection criteria were used: a) willingness to participate in the study; b) availability during the schedule of data collection; c) the extent of participation in DRRM activity, and d) interest in sharing knowledge and experiences in disaster media during a disaster/typhoon.

To ensure that the formulated research problems will be addressed by the target research participants, a survey questionnaire was constructed, pretested, and validated by this researcher to ensure reliability and validity the same survey questionnaire was used to gather data from the community stakeholders, which is composed of the head of the families in the above-mentioned municipality. Likewise, a semi-structured questionnaire for the key informant interviews (KIIs) was also formulated and used as an additional research instrument for the data gathering to substantiate the survey questionnaire.

Official documents such as DRRM for TD Usman and other relevant reports from the two studied barangays of Mayong and Maynonong in Tiwi Albay were collected and reviewed to substantiate the data obtained from various sources. Moreover, focus group discussions (FGDs) were also conducted to confirm, clarify, and strengthen or correct the initially gathered data derived from the survey and KIIs. Qualitative data were presented using narratives based on the results of the Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) and Key Informant Interviews (KIIs). Quantitative data collected through surveys were analyzed using descriptive statistics and the empirical findings are presented in this Chapter in the form of tables and graphs.

Research Locale

This study was conducted in the barangays of Mayong and Maynonong in Tiwi, Albay. These barangays were chosen because these communities were greatly affected with Maynonong having experienced massive landslides and widespread flooding during TD Usman which caused many fatalities and damages to properties.

According to the UN Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (2019) report, 68 individuals died in the four provinces of Bicol, and 19 are still missing. Albay, Camarines Norte, Camarines Sur and Sorsogon were among the most affected provinces in the Bicol Region. The severe devastation caused by TD Usman in December 2018 clearly shows the high vulnerability of the communities in the study sites, not only to flooding and storm surges but also to landslides. Figure 4 displays the devastation caused by the disaster and TD Usman in Tiwi Albay.

Figure 4.

Aftermath scenarios of TD Usman in the localities of Tiwi, Albay.

Research Design

This study utilized a stratified sampling design, taking the most affected barangay and the least affected barangay as the strata. The selection of the locale of the study was done via purposive sampling. Tiwi, which is situated in the province of Albay, was purposely selected having been identified by the DRRM of Albay as the hardest-hit town by the concerned government agencies, particularly during the TD Usman.

The researcher then purposefully selected two (2) barangays, namely Mayong and Maynonong. According to 2020 census data, Mayong has a population of 1,687 with 427 households, while Maynonong has 987 and 221 households (PhilAtlas, n.d.) Slovin's Formula was used to calculate the sample size for each stratum. The formula was used because the researcher does not have enough information about the population behavior of the two barangays of Tiwi Albay. It is used to ensure reasonable accuracy of the data collected as it provides an idea of how large the sample size needs to be and can be used as a guide during the data collection (Ellen, n.d.).

It is computed as follows:

$$n = N / (1 + Ne^2)$$

whereas:

n = no. of samples

N = total household population

e = error margin/margin of error

The total number of households was considered in determining the number of sample sizes. The margin of error used in the study was 05.

Thus, applying Slovin's Formula,

For Barangay Mayong

$$n = N / (1+Ne^2)$$

$$n = 427 / (1 + 427 * .05^2)$$

$$n = 206$$

For Baragay Maynonong

$$n = N / (1+Ne^2)$$

$$n = 221 / (1 + 221 * .05^2)$$

$$n = 142$$

Thus, Mayong with 427 households, the calculated sample size was 206. For Maynonong, with 221 households, the calculated sample size was 142. These calculated samples, representing the head of the household or someone in authority, were used as respondents for the two studied barangays.

Data Gathering Instruments

The main data-gathering tool to collect quantitative data was the questionnaire crafted by the researcher, tailor-fitted for the study. The questionnaire uses a five-point Likert scale to measure indicators of timeliness, accuracy, understandability, and relevance, the criteria used in determining the effectiveness of the disaster media as communication/information channels.

To ensure the understandability and comprehensiveness of the questionnaire, it was translated into the dialect spoken by residents of Tiwi, Albay. The questionnaire

was pre-tested on 10 residents of Sto. Domingo, Albay before the actual administration to the target respondents.

An unstructured in-depth interview guide for selected barangay residents was also developed and used in this study. The data will substantiate the survey instrument's responses. Like the questionnaire, the interview guide questions for the Key Informant Interview (KII) and Focus Group Discussion (FGD) were constructed in English and translated into the dialect spoken by the informant. These KII and FGD interview guides are also pre-tested with selected residents before the actual administration to the target respondents.

During KII and FGD, a digital voice recorder was used to record each interview with the informant. The recorded raw data from the KIIs and FGDs were transcribed verbatim and encoded as a written document for this research using a word processor. The data from the interview was used to substantiate the interpretation of the research findings from the quantitative data.

Research Participants

A total of 348 respondents from the subject barangays participated in the study, totaling 174 males and 174 females. The socio-demographic characteristics of these respondents were analyzed using descriptive statistics including frequencies and percentages.

The socio-demographic characteristics present 348 respondents in the two barangays covered by the study. Overall, there was an equal number of respondents with 50 percent male and 50 percent female. Barangay Mayong may have a slightly higher percentage of female respondents than males (53%), and Barangay

Maynonong has slightly more male respondents (54%) than females against their respective total number of respondents but this was even out when analyzed in the overall numbers of respondents from the two barangays. This is presented in Table 1.

Table 1.

Demographic characteristics of respondents.

Variable	Barangay Mayong (N=206)		Barangay Maynonong (n=142)		OVERALL (N=348)	
	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%
Sex						
Male	97	47	77	54	174	50
Female	109	53	65	46	174	50
	206	100	142	100	348	100
Age						
21-30 yrs old	29	14	18	13	47	13
31-40 yrs old	80	38	50	35	130	38
41-50 yrs old	69	34	62	44	131	38
51-60 yrs old	28	14	12	8	40	11
	206	100	142	100	348	100
Employment						
Farmer	96	47	49	34	145	42
Fisherman	12	6	56	40	68	19
Businessman	32	16	13	9	45	13
Self-employed	50	24	18	13	68	20
Unemployed	16	7	6	4	22	6
	206	100	142	100	348	100

The data also shows that 75 percent of the respondents were in the 31-50 age group, meaning they were neither too young nor too old. This finding is also consistent with the numbers in the two barangays studied.

The majority of respondents in the two barangays studied were farmers and fishermen. A small number of respondents (20%) reported that they were self-employed, including residents who owned their sari-sari stores.

Statistical Treatment and Analysis

Frequencies, percentages, mean, and ranks were used in the statistical treatment and analysis of data. Frequencies and percentages were used in

determining the characteristics of the respondents in the demographic profile while calculating the average mean and ranking provided an insight of what was the typical value or preference of the respondents in identifying the sets of data presented such as the communication channels and communication tools used during disasters and TD Usman, their preference of community influencers, active communication networks and in determining the common problems encountered during disasters. The Likert scale was used as an instrument to measure their beliefs and perceptions of the effectiveness of the disaster communication channels and sources of information. It has provided insight into the respondents' thoughts on how effective the variables are in terms of timeliness, accuracy, relevance, and understandability of the information. It utilized a five-point scale where the respondents rated their level of agreement in five points with 5 as the highest point, 3 as the middle or the usual average point, and 1 as the lowest point.

Essentially, to illustrate the data and present an overall idea, tables and graphs were also used.

Chapter IV

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter discusses the results of the study according to the order of research objectives. It presents the analysis and interpretation of quantitative and qualitative data on disaster media channels of communication and sources of information and their effectiveness on DRRM in Albay.

Utilization of disaster media as communication channels/sources of information by people affected by TD Usman

Community Influencers

To understand the local community influencers in Barangay Mayong and Maynonong in Tiwi Albay, the respondents identified the most believable community influencers in the locality being followed and /or sought by the people. Community influencers are existing members of the community who have built an audience and are thought leaders like local officials. Vanevska, (2022) described community influencers as individuals who are likely to appear with audiences who trust their opinions and advice. She emphasized that by collaborating with an influencer, the community may get the attention of its audience.

The respondents were asked to choose the influencers in the community that they follow during disasters to get messages and updates.

The respondents were allowed to check more than one influencer. The local officials were mentioned the most by the respondents in the two barangays. Overall, the second most mentioned community influencer was the family. However, for barangay Mayong it was the immediate neighbor.

The third most mentioned by the two barangay respondents was immediate or nearest neighbor. However, it was family for barangay Mayong and kumpare/kumare for barangay Maynonong. The least mentioned community influencers were the religious leaders. Table 2 shows the community influencers they followed during disasters.

Table 2.

Community Influencers followed by Barangay Mayong and Maynonong.

Community Influencers Followed by the Barangay	Mayong		Maynonong		Total	
	Responses	Rank	Responses	Rank	Responses	Rank
Local Officials	155	1	126	1	281	1
Family	80	3	115	2	195	2
Immediate/Nearest Neighbor	114	2	63	4	177	3
Kumpare/Kumare	48	5	65	3	113	4
Religious Leaders	49	4	58	5	107	5

The key informant interviews of selected research participants show that it was the local officials who had the privilege of securing the trust of the communities of barangays Mayong and Maynonong. The key informants emphasized that local officials, with the communication resources and direct access to information such as situational reports and weather updates, will be followed by their constituents, regardless of whether this information is updated, valid, and authorized. It was also reported that local officials have maintained their integrity as communicators and influencers. One of the interviewed respondents said:

“Mas maray maghapot kina kapitan o sa mga kagawad ta sinda an trained na sa disaster response; igwa man sinda pigsusunod na protocol.” (KII No.2).

(It would be better to ask for information from the barangay chair or barangay council members because they were trained in disaster response, and they have protocol)

These findings suggest that local officials are indeed faithful to their mandates. In R.A. 10121 or the Philippine Disaster Reduction and Management Act, barangay officials are expected to respond during calamities or disasters since they are the authorities closest to ground zero. These regulations guarantee that barangay officials are responsible for reducing and managing disaster risks, and they need to take proactive measures and strengthen disaster preparedness.

Moreover, these findings also corroborated several provisions under RA 7160 or the Local Government Code, Clause 88.b.6, which explains that whenever necessary the Punong Barangays will need to organize and lead an emergency response team to maintain peace and order within the barangay if there is a catastrophic emergency. Some respondents are one in saying that:

“Pag may bagyo at sakuna nag-iikot man sina Kap nagbabandilyo para maabisuhan an mga tawo.”*

(During typhoons/disasters, the barangay captain and barangay officials go around the barangay to inform the people and advise them of what to do.)

**bandilyo” or bandillo is to announce loudly usually using a megaphone*

As reflected in the various laws, creeds, decrees, and acts of the Philippines, the local government units, including the barangay councils, are mandated to ensure the safety of their constituents by implementing the prevention and mitigation programs of DRRM to lessen the negative impact of disasters.

The family, immediate/nearest neighbor, and kumpare/kumare are some of the major information channels and community influencers in Tiwi, Albay. They also use social information channels during a disaster to alert the public where help is located and needed and when they plan to reach hard areas.

The local officials were among the top community influencers chosen by the study respondents during calamities or disasters. According to them:

“Mas maray man giraray na tubudan si kap ta sinda man nakaaram kun ano an advise ninda susunudon mi.”

(It is better to heed the advice of the Barangay Chairman because they know better, we will follow his advice)

Moreover, the respondents also reported:

“May mga training po sa disaster an mga opisyaales kan barangay kaya aram man ninda an gigibuhon kun may bagyo o kalamidad.”

(Barangay officials are also trained in disaster [response] so they know what to do when a typhoon or calamity strikes.)

Figure 5 shows the community influencers in the two study communities.

Figure 5. *Community Influencers in barangays Mayong and Maynonong of Tiwi, Albay.*

According to Maskey (2012), the family, immediate/nearest neighbor, and kumpare/kumare play a vital role in reducing the impact of a disaster. They provide up-to-the-minute news information in times of disaster by directly reporting to the local governments and other authorities the road closure updates, evacuation routes, designated help areas, shelter locations, and other related information. Further, these influencers use their own social media accounts to share information about their well-being with family and friends, including their status and location on various social media networks, and thus, notify family members and friends that they are alright.

As influencers, the local officials are mostly sought by the local communities of both Mayong and Maynonong in times of disaster/typhoons. The local officials tended to upload photos or videos to social media networks for help in documenting what was happening right there before their eyes, particularly the damages to the affected areas. Their uploads help in identifying survivors, and in turn, emergency personnel will be

aware of the severity of the situation, which can be seen by the public faster than the news stations and newspapers can broadcast. As community influencers, they provided real-time information to law enforcement, officials, and the general public, as well as directly to their friends and family.

When other forms of communication are cut off due to a disaster, social media still exists and is readily accessible because of the presence of community influencers. If all else fails such as electricity, landlines, electricity, computers, etc., these social media influencers still have mobile phones that can access the internet and download apps. As such, they are becoming increasingly important in the field of disaster preparedness, recovery, and relief.

A total of 107 respondents chose religious leaders in the two communities as the least media communicators/influencers in their barangays. According to Mark Stibich in his treatise on Psychology of Religion, faith communities, where religious leaders belong, can be a source of guidance and comfort providing a sense of connection and community especially when critical events happen. Thus, religious leaders can play a significant role in shaping attitudes, opinions, and behaviors because their members also trust them. After the disaster, these religious leaders used social media to help others find their relatives and pets and even track their personal belongings. They also assist the public with donation efforts and relief funds that the affected individuals will need such as clothing, non-perishable goods, and other basic items, as well as a safe place to stay.

The religious leaders have the power to raise awareness and influence attitudes, behaviors, and practices to prevent and mitigate disaster risk by shaping the social values of the people in the community in line with faith-based teachings.

Given these findings, it is safe to assume that the interplay of traditional media, social media, the “influencers” and the “inactives” was apparent in the settings of this study. The dominant use of traditional media such as radio and TV, as well as the reliance on “influencers” are the established crisis communications strategies in barangay Maynonong and Mayong.

Disaster media channels utilized by the barangays including the crisis communication framework or system in place

During and after a disaster, effective disaster communication tools and channels must be in place. Successful coordination of response efforts to limit morbidity and disease can be facilitated when a communication system is established. Likewise, public and private organizations need to establish communication channels with various stakeholders early and inform them frequently of what is happening in their communities. Then, orderly response plans and actions can be implemented and prevent people from panicking.

The government and other decision-makers also need to know what response efforts are ongoing and what type of further assistance is required to coordinate relief operations. Health professionals assisting the communities during a disaster should assess which health risks or illnesses are increasing and strategize how best to advise their patients to remain calm while working in the field. They should inform the public where to seek help in an emergency to protect themselves and their families. Disaster media platforms for this health information include press releases and media interviews, Internet articles and social media, town hall forums, and frequent and timely communications among responders (MEDFORD-Davis and Kapur, 2017)

The study sought to determine what type of channels of communication and the sources of information, including the crisis communication framework or system, are in place in the study barangays. What was the acquired information during the disaster and TD Usman and where did they obtain the said information?

Channels of communication and sources of information refer to the several ways by which a message is delivered to inform the people of what's happening, particularly during a time of crisis or emergency. In times of crisis, especially during typhoons or disasters, messages will be delivered in many ways, which could be high-tech delivery (i.e., two-way internet channels used with social media) or low-tech delivery (i.e., handwritten flyers or messages painted on buildings or any visible area), depending on the available channels and tools of communication available in the area (CERC: Other Communication Channels, 2014).

Between traditional and rapid electronic media, there are more choices for communication channels than ever in human history (Communication at Work, n.d.). However, each has its unique advantages and disadvantages that make it appropriate or inappropriate for specific situations (Communication at Work, n.d.).

According to the UN Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (2014), disaster-media communications are a form of aid. Selecting the most appropriate channels and methods for communication is deemed important, particularly in reaching out to the disrupted communities during typhoons and disasters. In addition, it also gets adequate information promptly and accesses critical life-saving information. This can also provide the right information, at the right time, through the right channels to save lives and decrease the loss of peoples' livelihoods and property. This is especially important in health risk communication, where respondents can

quickly feel excluded, and more people are fragmented, turning to specialized and localized outlets for news and information.

Figure 6 presents the summary of various disaster media channels of communication/information sources that provided the studied barangays in Tiwi, Albay

Figure 6.

The disaster media channels utilized by the barangays.

with much-needed disaster information/messages during disasters and typhoons.

Overall, television was the most dominant disaster media channel of communication and source of information with 296 responses. It was followed by local officials, chosen with 280 responses, and radio identified by 260 responses. Cellphones/SMS had 242 responses and family, with 194 responses.

These findings are corroborated by Lazer, Kennedy, & Margolin (2013). They reported that television remains the dominant means of finding information on emergencies, followed by cell phones and electronic media. Moreover, Adjusters International (n.d.) also reported that the top 10 communication methods used in a disaster setting are social media, mobile applications (apps), cell phones, landline telephones, satellite phones (satphones), two-way radio, citizens band radio (CB radio), amateur radio (HAM radio), police scanner, and word-of-mouth.

The least preferred channels of communication/sources of information by the respondents were kumpare/kumare, religious leaders, social media like FB, Twitter, YouTube, newspapers, and internet/websites.

In terms of the specific communication tools and channels utilized by the crisis communication system in place in barangays Mayong and Maynonong during disasters and typhoons, empirical findings revealed that television remains one of the most important sources of information. Households can use a TV antenna to watch local TV programs for free. Respondents also reported that some households have cable connections with a local TV network provider, DCTV and that most, if not all, subscribe to PLDT's direct-to-home (DTH) satellite provider, Signal TV.

Moreover, the findings show that prepaid subscriptions appear to be beneficial to the Maynonong and Mayong communities. Local officials were also reported by the respondents as one of the most accessible sources and/or channels of communication because they have constant formal meetings and encounters with the residents. Both barangays have very active Barangay Health Workers (BHWs) assigned in every purok or sitio, and they also reside in said communities. Any advisory or information is transmitted through their local officials and BHWs.

Another popular disaster media channel or communication tool utilized by the respondents is the radio. The radio is the least expensive and most practical source of information among the communities of Mayong, especially when people would want to know information outside of their localities other than entertainment.

However, the third most preferred communication channel in Maynonong is the family. This can be attributed to the fact that this barangay is small, with close-knit family ties. Their houses are closer to each other, and most of the residents are related to one another. Thus, access to information is easy, convenient, and just a stone's throw away. Nevertheless, the data show that both barangays still favor the use of television, local officials, and radio.

Table 3 exhibits the specific disaster media channels of communications/sources of information used by Barangay Officials during Disasters and typhoons based on the responses from the two studied barangays.

Table 3.

Channels of communication/sources of information utilized by the barangays of Mayong and Maynonong.

Channels of Communication/ Sources of Information	Mayong		Maynonong		Overall	
	F	Rank	F	Rank	F	Rank
Newspaper	32	9	11	11	43	10
Radio	148	3	113	4	261	3
TV (television)	168	1	128	1	296	1
Cellphone/SMS	135	4	108	5	243	4
Internet/Websites	15	11	18	10	33	11
Social Media (FB, Twitter, Youtube)	28	10	51	9	79	9
Immediate/Nearest Neighbor	113	5	63	7	176	6
Kumpare/Kumare	48	8	65	6	113	7
Family	79	6	115	3	194	5
Local Officials	155	2	125	2	280	2
Religious Leaders	49	7	58	8	107	8

In Mayong's normal situation, the least popular communication channels are the internet/website, social media, and newspapers. Just like Mayong, the least preferred communication channels/tools in the barangay of Maynonong are newspapers, the internet/websites, and social media. According to the respondents, these channels are not popular in rural communities. Moreover, the study respondents are household heads. They are more preoccupied with local livelihood activities than learning and accessing unfamiliar channels of communication.

Looking at their choices of disaster media communication channels, it is safe to assume that both communities are reliant on the traditional media, which are radio, and TV for information. The secondary channel is a cellphone that can transmit information via calls and text messages. These are the usual communication channels with or without disasters in rural communities as these are the most dominant quad media that can easily be accessed especially in times when they seek out information that is relevant to them for informed decisions. However, the downside of this is that TV and radio can only be accessible while the power supply is available in the area. Information will only be made available if these channels are operational with the help of the power supply; both for the radio station and for the household.

Meanwhile, access to information via cell phones may extend its use through the stored power supply. The timeliness, accuracy, and understandability of the information or messages might be hampered by the strength of the network signal and the sender's integrity for valid and clear information.

One notable channel of information identified by respondents was the local officials. This implies that the trust level of local officials as a disaster media channel is high because these people have direct contact with the agencies and sources of

disaster information. However, local officials may also fulfill the role of community influencers, able to disseminate information and influence opinions and decisions about disaster management and response. These people may not be social media savvy just like the rest of the community, but they can also access the radio, a popular source of information which also sources information either from social media or directly from agencies.

When a public health crisis evolves beyond 24 to 48 hours, the demand for information outside traditional media channels (i.e., radio, TV, newspaper, and news websites) increases, and public information officials must choose the appropriate method of disaster media communication to manage various audiences. Achieving effective communication with audiences depends on selecting effective methods of communication. This can be especially important in disaster risk reduction communication, where the audience can become disenfranchised quickly if they feel that they are not getting appropriate and adequate information (Orau Org, 2020).

Communication tools/devices utilized by the barangays, including the crisis communication framework or system operating in Tiwi Albay

In addition to identifying the disaster media communication channels/sources of information used during or when a disaster occurs, this study also aims to identify the communication tools or devices that local officials use to deliver information to the community during a disaster or typhoon.

The most widely used disaster media communication tools were megaphones, followed by cell phones, and radio. The least disaster media communication tool or device used by local officials during a calamity is a handheld radio such as a walkie-talkie/VHF.

Figure 7 presents the responses of the respondents in the communities of Mayong and Maynonong.

Figure 7.

Communication tools/devices utilized during disasters in the Brgy. Mayong and Maynonong in Tiwi, Albay.

The use of megaphones, cell phones, and radio by local officials in the Mayong and Manonong communities during disasters/typhoons could be attributed to the lack of electricity and thus the use of these portable, battery-operated communication devices is more applicable, sensible, and convenient for communicating all at once with people.

To barangay officials, however, the most applicable means of communicating with their constituents is by using a megaphone. They can address a large number of

the population at once by using a megaphone without additional costs. Sending text messages or making phone calls requires a load amount or a load subscription.

People in the community are also aware that in times of disaster/typhoon, their local officials resort to megaphones and are expected to wait for public advisories.

Moreover, the respondents' use of cell phones is a priority because they can also send and receive SMS coming from the authorities (local officials, MDRRMC/NDRRMC). By re-charging these gadgets with compact power banks, the respondents can maintain a connection with the authorities. This was supported by the Key Informant 1 response, saying:

“Para sako, mas madali gamiton an selpon ta maski brownout kun may battery pa, makaapod o makatext pa sa iba para maka-aram kun ano na an sabi tungkol sa bagyo.”

(For me, I find it easier to use a cellphone because even if the power is out already, and the cell phone battery is still charged, I can call or send a text message to other people to get information about the typhoon.)

Radio is another practical way of getting information during disasters. People can use the radio provided they have batteries stored for emergencies. Radio stations can transmit advisories and information if electricity and generators can provide them with transmission power.

It was reported that a combination of traditional (radio and hand-held radios) and digital (cell phones) tools are considered information or media channels during

disasters/typhoons. With this setup, updated information may be limited considering that these tools are reliant on the available power supply and only to a limited population. The respondents revealed that the radio may be their only source of information, or they may rely on updates from authorized agencies delivered using faster channels such as social media. Moreover, the use of cell phones during disasters may prove effective if there is an active and strong network signal as well as an available power supply. If these were cut off, disaster response would be delayed.

As observed from the experience of Region VIII during the onslaught of Typhoon Yolanda, disaster media communication tools should not be limited to cell phones since cellular signals can also fail. Those learning from the experience highly recommend the use of radio, VHF, and UHF as these can also be easily used in the event of a disaster/typhoon (Newbyth. ph, 2020).

Table 4 shows the communication tools or devices used by the respondents during TD Usman. Most respondents used cell phones, followed by megaphones, radio, and walkie-talkie/VHF.

Table 4.

Communication tools/devices utilized during TD Usman.

Communication tools/devices utilized during TD Usman	Mayong		Maynonong		Total	
	<i>f</i>	<i>rank</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>rank</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>rank</i>
Megaphone	108	1	71	2	176	2
Cellphone	91	2	123	1	213	1
Radio	84	3	59	3	143	3
Handheld Radio (Walkie-Talkie/VHF)	3	4	2	4	5	4

During TD Usman, cell phones and megaphones were the main disaster media communication tools/devices used by local officials. Maynonong barangay officials preferred the use of cell phones, instead of megaphones, because their location gets

better connectivity for sending and receiving text messages, and megaphones can suitably address a large number of communities at once. However, Mayong barangay officials utilized megaphones as disaster media communication tools/devices during TD Usman due to the weaker signal of cell phones. These findings were corroborated by the study of Mukhopadhyay & Bhattacharjee, (2015) regarding the use of IT in emergency and disaster management. In their study, the researchers reported that landlines and mobile phones play a significant role in providing alerts/warnings about the danger of impending disasters in communities. They emphasized that the use of cell phones to inform the concerned community of disaster warnings may save many lives in the community, just like what happened in the 2004 Tsunami in South Asian Countries, where the use of cell phones also saved many lives in the coastal region.

In addition to the identified disaster media communication tools/devices, residents and local officials of barangays Mayong and Manonong use television and radio to access or receive information about disasters. According to the respondents, they are more familiar with traditional media than digital ICTs such as the internet/websites, social media, and less popular media.

While local officials are also considered channels of communication, they are also users of digital and mechanical tools of communication. The use of these traditional media means that access to digital media and ICT is limited, and/or its capabilities have not yet been explored for optimal use during disasters.

Limitations on the use of other disaster media communication tools during the disaster may have hindered the delivery of timely and relevant information about Typhoon Usman. While most sources of information disseminate information faster by utilizing other tools and channels such as social media platforms, real-time and on-

time information cannot be as fast and as wide as when it is channeled to social media. Aside from these disaster media communication tools, other communication technologies (i.e., cell broadcasting, satellite radio, internet or e-mail, radio, and others) were also utilized by the LGU to warn and further inform the people of the communities in case of disaster to save more lives (Mukhopadhyay & Bhattacharjee, 2015).

Frequency of use of disaster media channels of communications during disasters and TD Usman

The respondents were asked to rate the frequency of use of disaster media communication channels /sources of information during a disaster and TD Usman.

Results show that local officials ranked 1, television ranked 2, and cell phones ranked 3. The lowest-rated channels were ranked 11, newspaper; ranked 10, internet, and ranked 9, social media.

The study respondents were asked how often they used the disaster media communication/sources of information during a disaster. For each item, they have to choose if usage means always, often, sometimes, seldom, or never been used. The mean response was obtained for each item.

The respondents' frequency of use of disaster media communication/sources of information during a disaster was obtained. The communities of Mayong and Maynonong always go to the local officials with a mean of 4.86, followed by television with a mean of 4.85, cell phones with a mean of 4.71, and religious leaders, with a mean of 4.61. This finding implies that their local officials are very accessible, can be reached at any time by any practical means, and that they trust the information coming from them.

Table 5 presents the respondents' frequency of use of disaster media communication/sources of information during a disaster.

Table 5.

The respondents' frequency of use of disaster media channels of communication during disasters.

Channels of communication/sources of information during disasters	During disasters	During TD Usman	Overall Mean	Interpretation
	Mean	Mean		
Newspaper	3.53	3.21	3.37	sometimes
Radio	4.48	4.61	4.55	often
TV (television)	4.87	4.83	4.85	always
Cellphone/SMS (ICT)	4.79	4.62	4.71	always
Internet/Websites (ICT)	3.44	3.24	3.34	sometimes
Social Media (FB, Twitter, Youtube)	3.65	3.42	3.54	often
Immediate/Nearest Neighbor	4.4	3.73	4.1	often
Kumpare/Kumare	4.38	3.80	4.09	often
Family	4.45	4.12	4.29	often
Local Officials	4.83	4.94	4.89	always
Religious Leaders	4.59	4.73	4.66	always

The newspapers, the internet, and social media were only used sometimes by the respondents, which were generally not utilized during disasters. This is true because the newspaper is not available in their communities. Internet and social media are not popular with the respondents who are also the decision-makers of the household due to the absence of internet or Wi-Fi.

It is presumed that cell phones were used simply for sending or receiving text messages and calls. Although cell phones can be utilized to access the internet and social media platforms, respondents however listed social media and the internet as the least they utilize during disasters in

terms of frequency as indicated in the results. During TD Usman, the respondents frequently utilize the same communication channels whenever there are typhoons or weather disturbances. It means that their local officials, television, and cell phones are practically more accessible than any other means.

The communities of Mayong and Maynonong were considered “inactive” and “followers” of the local officials, who are regarded as the “community influencers” in the social-mediated communication theory, and are indirect receivers of information sourced by their local officials. These local officials have communication tools that can access direct information from the local agencies on disaster management and other information from social media, aside from the traditional media which are more popular in their communities.

Regarding the frequency of use during TD Usman, the respondents typically followed the local officials, television, and cell phones. The least followed or preferred were newspapers, the internet, and social media.

During TD Usman, the respondents always utilized local officials, television, cell phones, and radio, with a mean use of 4.94, 4.83, 4.71, and 4.55 respectively.

The least affected barangay of Mayong listed Local Officials, TV & cellphones, and radio as the top three (3) sources of communication channels that they have frequently utilized during the onslaught of TD Usman. The most affected barangay of Maynonong meanwhile, listed TV, Local Officials, and radio as the most frequently utilized channels during TD Usman. A strong reliance on these channels implies that for them, these media can be easily accessed and that they have higher confidence in obtaining updated information about weather disturbances than the other identified

channels of communication in their communities. Table 6 presents the data for this.

Table 6.

The respondents' frequency of use of disaster media channels of communication during TD Usman.

Channels of Communication/ Sources of Information	Mayong		Maynonong		Total	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	VI	Mean	Interpretation
Newspaper	3.98	<i>almost always</i>	2.44	<i>seldom</i>	3.21	sometimes
Radio	4.61	<i>always</i>	4.61	<i>always</i>	4.61	always
TV (television)	4.69	<i>always</i>	4.96	<i>always</i>	4.83	always
Cellphone/SMS (ICT)	4.69	<i>always</i>	4.54	<i>always</i>	4.62	always
Internet/Websites (ICT)	3.40	<i>sometimes</i>	3.08	<i>sometimes</i>	3.24	sometimes
Social Media (FB, Twitter, Youtube)	3.73	<i>almost always</i>	3.11	<i>sometimes</i>	3.42	sometimes
Immediate/Nearest Neighbor	4.41	<i>almost always</i>	3.19	<i>sometimes</i>	3.80	almost always
Kumpare/Kumare	4.47	<i>almost always</i>	3.10	<i>sometimes</i>	3.79	almost always
Family	4.52	<i>always</i>	3.71	<i>almost always</i>	4.12	almost always
Local Officials	4.98	<i>always</i>	4.89	<i>always</i>	4.94	always
Religious Leaders	4.80	<i>always</i>	4.66	<i>always</i>	4.73	always

During TD Usman, the respondents in both barangays utilized the same channels. Local officials, TV, and cell phones are the most frequently utilized. This implies that these traditional media channels are preferred more than any other media channels or tools.

Communication networks operational in the municipality of Tiwi, Albay

To ascertain which communication networks are operational in the study communities as communication facilities, this research identifies the specific communication networks available in Tiwi Albay.

Various communication networks actively exist in the municipality of Tiwi, Albay. A total of 301 respondents (88%) identified SMART as the number one communication network operational in their communities as a communication facility. It was followed by GLOBE with 277 respondents (81%) as seen in Figure 8.

DCTV and PLDT networks are the other communication facilities existing in the communities.

Figure 8.

Active communication networks in the municipality of Tiwi, Albay.

The KIIs reveal that SMART ensures the availability and rapid restoration of services in areas that have damaged infrastructure, including power lines. SMART ensures the reliability of its services, and in the event of distress, it provides services such as *libreng tawag* (free calls), charging, and Wi-Fi access to affected residents and responders. (reliefweb.int/report, 2016)

GLOBE, on the other hand, assists communities in terms of building better network infrastructure while continuously assessing risks and impacts to ensure that it can provide telecommunications services to affected areas. To better assist the affected communities in times of disaster/typhoon, GLOBE has also launched programs to immediately respond to and recover from major disasters, such as helping

governments with search and rescue efforts while providing the much-needed communications services to communities (globe.com.ph., 2021)

Effectiveness of the disaster media communication channels used by the study barangays in making informed decisions about DRRM

Each disaster or typhoon serves as a learning opportunity on how to communicate better to mitigate disaster risk and save more lives and properties. Several retrospective studies have tried to document these lessons by determining how the public understood the quad media messages communicated to them during disasters or tropical depressions (Medfor-Davis and Kapur, 2017). Additionally, gaps in disaster or tropical depression communication plans, such as technical or complex instructions, can make it easy for communities to misinterpret information. Ineffective communication methods can result in poor communication or poor dissemination of information, preventing it from reaching much-needed target communities in the event of a typhoon or disaster (Medfor-Davis and Kapur, 2017).

Hence, effective disaster media communication channels that are quick, concise, and consistent are vital in managing an emergency response. Disaster or tropical depression demands messages that are said to be simple, consistent, and updated regularly and frequently. Without proper and effective communication channels, there is always an opportunity to mislead or misdirect the community, which in turn will create more problems in the response efforts. Thus, if not effectively managed, it would lead to another chaos in the future.

The study's third research question revolves around the assessment of how effective the disaster media communication channels used by barangays Mayong and

Maynonong in making informed decisions about DRRM in Tiwi Albay, particularly in terms of timeliness, accuracy, relevance, and understandability. The result of this study would provide timely information during disasters and a tropical depression shortly. This finding will contribute to a quick call to action by the people affected by the weather disturbances for a more effective community engagement as well as to enable local government to bolster disaster preparedness thus avoiding and reducing the harm caused by disasters.

Table 7 summarizes the study participants' perceived effectiveness of the disaster media communication channels/sources of information in making informed decisions about DRRM in terms of timeliness, accuracy, relevance; and understandability in Tiwi, Albay.

Table 7.

Perceived effectiveness of the disaster media communication channels used by the study barangays in making informed decisions about DRRM in Tiwi, Albay.

Disaster Media Channels of Communication/Sources of Information	Timeliness Mean	Accuracy Mean	Relevance Mean	Understandability Mean	Overall Mean and Interpretation
TV (television)	4.72	4.73	4.70	4.75	4.73 Extremely Effective
Radio	4.62	4.65	4.60	4.60	4.62 Extremely Effective
Cellphone/SMS	4.54	4.71	4.47	4.66	4.60 Extremely Effective
Newspaper	4.24	4.33	3.75	4.20	4.13 Very Effective
Social Media (FB, Twitter, YouTube)	3.95	3.85	3.96	4.10	3.97 Very Effective
Internet/Websites	3.90	3.61	3.68	3.82	3.75 Very Effective
Overall	4.33	4.31	4.19	4.36	4.30 Very Effective

The overall results show that the six (6) identified disaster media channels, television, radio, cell phone/SMS, newspapers, social media (i.e., FB, Twitter,

YouTube, etc.), and internet/websites, were considered “very effective” disaster media communication channels/sources of information with an overall mean of 4.30.

The data in Table 7 shows that television, radio, and cellphone/SMS were rated as the most “extremely effective” disaster media communication channels/sources of information. This finding implies that the respondents considered these communication channels as the most authoritative and influential disaster media platforms, particularly in terms of ensuring the widest distribution of messages and reaching the target audiences crucial to the public’s health and safety as well as to informed decisions about DRRM in Tiwi Albay.

Timeliness

Table 8 displays the results of the assessment of the research participants.

Table 8.

Perceived effectiveness of disaster media communication channels as to timeliness.

Disaster Communication Channels According to Timeliness	Mayong	Maynonong	Overall	Interpretation
	(N=203)	N=141)	Mean	
	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Mean</i>	(N=344)	
TV (television)	4.48	4.98	4.73	Very Timely
Cellphone/SMS (ICT)	4.49	4.93	4.71	Very Timely
Radio	4.34	4.95	4.65	Very Timely
Newspaper	4.46	4.20	4.33	Moderately Timely
Social Media (FB, Twitter, YouTube)	3.76	3.93	3.85	Moderately Timely
Internet/Websites (ICT)	3.50	3.72	3.61	Moderately Timely
Overall	4.17	4.45	4.31	Moderately Timely

As shown in the table, television provides very timely information, with a mean of 4.73 to the affected communities during disasters and typhoons. Viewers in any household with a TV can get disaster information updates. Even though few channels

are sharing various content throughout the Bicol Region, television is still the main source of post-disaster information. It is one of the most authoritative and influential disaster media based on the gathered data in the study barangays.

Moreover, the concept of timeliness has been attributed to television because local TV stations, particularly GMA 7 and ABS-CBN-Bicol, provide daily news broadcasts and can be accessed anytime provided there is a power supply. Events, local issues, and updates, including weather disturbances and disasters, are aired in the daily news program.

Cell Phone/SMS, with a mean of 4.71 and radio, with a 4.65 mean, provide very timely communication to intended audiences in the past, and are very economical to use. For instance, television, cell phone/SMS, and radio play a significant role in the wake of the disaster and tropical depression in Tiwi, Albay, by providing accurate and timely information to the affected communities, enhancing their awareness and extending outreach to appropriate authorities. While disaster media communication channels and tools pave the way for closing information gaps at different levels of the communication process, it has been observed that not everyone can work effectively during a disaster.

On the other hand, the disaster media that displayed moderately timeliness in communicating with the public during disasters and typhoons are newspapers (mean=4.33), followed by social media (mean=3.85), and internet/websites (mean=3.61). This could be because during disasters, the far-flung community of Mayong may no longer have access to the power supply. Instead, they can readily inquire or communicate with their neighbors, usually their *kumpares* and *kumares*, for timely information. In the barangay communities studied, word-of-mouth also emerged

as an important form of disaster media crisis communication to connect with friends and family.

According to the interviewed respondents, they want to learn what other families in their communities are doing in response to the crisis. They opined that disaster crises have a powerful emotional impact on them. Hence, they want to share the experience with friends and family. It is also an opportunity to determine and confirm if other people are alive and safe. To ensure that they can immediately communicate with loved ones, friends and relatives, they utilize a combination of any or all of these disaster media communication channels as a strategy to reach a broad audience. During a crisis, the respondents reported the use of as many disaster communication channels/sources of information as possible to ensure the widest distribution of messages. Thus, close coordination and consistency of communication channels/messages with the community are considered important. While the message needs to be adapted to the various communication channels of the chosen disaster media, consistency is still key.

Accuracy

The respondents were asked to identify which among the disaster media channels of information is considered accurate or correct and truthful in providing needed information during disasters.

Overall, the respondents assessed the information being relayed by the communication channel as accurate, with a mean of 4.33.

Table 9 presents the findings on the accuracy, correctness, and veracity of the required information during a disaster.

Table 9.

Perceived effectiveness of disaster media communication channels as to accuracy.

Disaster Communication Channels According to Accuracy	Mayong (N=203)	Maynonong N=141)	Overall Mean (N=344)	Verbal Interpretation
	Mean	Mean		
TV (television)	4.47	4.97	4.72	Very Accurate
Radio	4.34	4.89	4.62	Very Accurate
Cellphone/SMS (ICT)	4.36	4.72	4.54	Very Accurate
Newspaper	4.29	4.18	4.24	Accurate
Social Media (FB, Twitter, YouTube)	4.04	3.85	3.95	Accurate
Internet/Websites (ICT)	4.11	3.68	3.90	Accurate
Overall	4.27	4.38	4.33	Accurate

4.500- 5.000 - Very Accurate
 3.500-4.499 - Accurate
 2.500-3.499 - Moderately Accurate
 1.500-2.499 - Less Accurate
 1.000-1.499 - Not Accurate

In terms of the accuracy of specific disaster media channels/information sources, the top four communications channels that provide very accurate information at the time of a disaster are TV, with a mean of 4.72, followed by radio (mean=4.62) and cellphones/SMS ICT, with a mean of 4.54. On the other hand, newspapers (mean=4.24), social media (mean=3.95), and internet/websites (mean=3.90) were the least popular of the identified disaster media channels/sources/information as far as accuracy is concerned.

The results indicate the respondents believe that some of the disaster media channels/information sources used by local officials provide accurate information during a disaster/typhoon. Considering their resources which are way limited (access to power supply, location, technology, and telecommunication signals), the

respondents seemed to have no other choice but to get reliable or truthful information from the available disaster media channels aside from local officials.

After TV, radio is the second most accurate disaster media channel/source of information and mobile/text (ICT) is the third. Both communities put their trust and confidence in TV, cell phone/SMS (ICT), radio, and local officials as the major sources of accurate disaster information. When disasters occur, the integrity of local officials as a source of accurate information is undoubtedly maintained. Whether or not local officials have been looking for accurate information does not matter as their source, the reliability of true information depends on local officials.

Relevance

To ascertain which communication channels provide relevant information during disasters or weather disturbances, the respondents' preferences are shown in Table 10.

Table 10.

Perceived effectiveness of disaster media communication channels as to relevance.

Disaster Communication Channels According to Relevance	Mayong (N=203)	Maynonong N=141)	Overall Mean (N=344)	Verbal Interpretation
	Mean	Mean		
TV (television)	4.41	4.98	4.70	Very Relevant
Radio	4.30	4.89	4.60	Very Relevant
Cellphone/SMS (ICT)	4.39	4.54	4.47	Relevant
Social Media (FB, Twitter, YouTube)	4.07	3.85	3.96	Relevant
Newspaper	4.33	3.17	3.75	Relevant
Internet/Websites (ICT)	3.81	3.54	3.68	Relevant
Overall	4.22	4.16	4.19	Relevant

4.500- 5.000 - Very Relevant
3.500-4.499 - Relevant
2.500-3.499 - Moderately Relevant
1.500-2.499 - Less Relevant
1.000-1.499 - Not Relevant

As shown in Table 10, television (mean=4.70) and radio (mean=4.60) are rated as relevant disaster communication channels. According to Claudy (2014), for many

decades, radio and television have been used as the primary sources of critical information for the public in the event of disasters such as tropical storms, floods, earthquakes, tsunamis, mass transportation accidents, and industrial or technological catastrophes. Radio and television as disaster media also play an important role before, during, and after a disaster/typhoon. They provide reliable peer-to-peer delivery of much-needed information, including safety advisories and instructions to the public especially to disaster/typhoon responders.

Kokemuller (2019) emphasizes that each of these disaster media provides different message formats. Television offers one of the widest ranges of sensory appeal and creative opportunities, so you can present your story through characters, action, visual effects, written and oral copy as well as sound and product demonstrations. However, radio has no visual component, and the effectiveness of the message is based solely on creative copywriting combined with effective voice and narrative. Social media can range from video streaming on YouTube to short text transcripts on Twitter or Facebook.

In general, both barangays still utilize traditional media such as TV, and radio because they still believe that these media can give them relevant information. An interesting finding also pointed out that relevance is again attributed to television. Local TV programs provide daily local news and updates that their communities find significant to their daily lives, especially during calamities and disasters. They emphasized that live coverage and news broadcasts of local issues and events are provided by the local TV news programs.

Understandability

The respondents were asked about the media channels that provide them with information that is readily understood. Table 11 shows the responses of the study participants.

Table 11.

Perceived effectiveness of disaster media communication channels as to understandability.

Queer Communication Channels According to Understandability	Mayong N=203)	Maynonong N=141)	Overall Mean (N=344)	Verbal Interpretation
	Mean	Mean		
TV (television)	4.52	4.98	4.75	Very Understandable
Radio	4.30	4.89	4.60	Very Understandable
Cellphone/SMS (ICT)	4.46	4.86	4.66	Very Understandable
Social Media (FB, Twitter, YouTube)	4.03	4.16	4.10	Understandable
Newspaper	4.38	4.01	4.20	Understandable
Internet/Websites (ICT)	3.58	4.05	3.82	Understandable
Overall	4.21	4.49	4.35	Understandable

4.500- 5.000 - *Very Understandable*

3.500-4.499 - *Understandable*

2.500-3.499 - *Moderately Understandable*

1.500-2.499 - *Less Understandable*

1.000-1.499 - *Not Understandable*

Overall, the results show that the disaster media communication channels used are effective in terms of understandability, with a mean of 4.35. Table 11 shows that TV, radio, and cellphone/SMS were identified as effective communication channels based on understandability. These three (3) channels were rated as very easy to understand. Other disaster media communication channels like newspapers, social media such as FB, Twitter, YouTube, and internet/websites are rated easy to understand.

However, Mayong and Maynonong still classify TV, radio, and cell phones as channels that can provide them with understandable information during a disaster.

The use of vernacular language as a medium of communication provides them with a better understanding of the situation or experiences during disasters.

Communicating with the same context and meaning to a particular audience is imperative in managing or responding to crises or disasters. This is one of the basic factors in arriving at a common understanding to enforce a decision or action. For an effective response, a source or an influencer should be understood enough by the target audience or recipients of the information.

Problems or challenges encountered in Utilizing disaster media channels and the preparations for Maintaining communication during disasters

Despite massive technological changes taking place in the country today, disaster media communication problems persist. These communication problems include lack of communication networks, system failure, poor slow internet connection, improper choice of communication channels, and incompatibility between communication systems being used by different agencies, lack of capabilities of the local officials managing appropriate quad media platforms in times of disaster/typhoon. While disaster media is now the most efficient method of delivering emergency response messages in a contemporary urban crisis scenario in the aftermath of a disaster/typhoon, valuable spatially related information can often be difficult to pinpoint within unhelpful or speculative disaster media.

The lack of communication networks or service providers with the most number of responses, poor/slow internet connection particularly when using the internet, cellphone, and social media, only radio can be accessed during a disaster due to the termination of electricity supply and the inefficient use of technology and other sources of information, difficulty in accessing disaster media due to expensive data

connections, improper choice of communication channels - getting information from neighbors and relatives when radio, television, social media are unavailable and the proliferation of fake news are listed as the problems or challenges encountered by the respondents in utilizing disaster media channels.

Table 12 shows the major problems/challenges encountered by the study participants on disaster media channels of communication.

Table 12.

Problems or challenges encountered by the respondents in utilizing disaster media channels.

Problems or challenges encountered in utilizing disaster media channels	Mayong		Maynonong		Total	
	No. of responses	rank	No. of responses	rank	No. of responses	rank
There is a lack of communication networks or service providers in the locality	111	1	117	3	228	1
When using the internet, cellphone and social media, there is a poor/slow connection	75	3	120	1	195	2
Social Media cannot be accessed due to expensive data connections.	37	5	118	2	155	4
Only radio can be accessed during a disaster for a while due to the termination of power supply and inefficient use of technology by the sources of information	85	2	96	4	181	3
When radio, TV, and social media cannot be accessed, information is sought from neighbors and kin (poor choice of communication channels)	38	4	86	6	124	5
There is a proliferation of fake news.	29	7	88	5	117	6
There are too many information sources and cannot identify which one is to be trusted.	36	6	63	7	99	7
The advisories/messages/information cannot be understood. (Poor/unclear message delivery)	10	9.5	14	10	24	10
The agency/agencies sending the information shares incorrect information (lack of trust to the information source)	10	9.5	17	8.5	27	9
Local officials do not have a capability to use and maintain appropriate and effective communication channels	12	8	17	8.5	29	8

The KII's key results support these findings. Nearly all the interviewed respondents said that a major challenge in crisis communication is the lack of a communication network or service provider in their area. Mayong is the most remote barangay in Tiwi Albay, and there is no cell site for SMART and Globe networks to transmit strong digital mobile communication signals.

Local cable TV service providers offer TV subscription packages with internet access only in the main towns of Tiwi and adjacent barangays, including Maynonong. For both communities, the challenge in accessing digital wireless communications is evident due to the lack of structures and facilities for faster connectivity to mobile and Internet communications.

The expensive data charges when accessing the internet for social media is another identified challenge. For rural residents who live to maintain their basic daily needs, the cost of data connectivity is the least of the priority. In addition, radio can be freely accessed via Amplified and Frequency Modulations, but these can only be utilized while the electrical power supply is available. The power supply is the first of the utilities to go off during disasters, especially typhoons,

The respondents also reported that the lack of communication facilities or structures to amplify the signal of digital and mobile communications could hinder authorities from effectively responding to disasters. Communication processes between sources and receivers of information may be improved by utilizing a variety of digital media and communication platforms, facilities, and resources to meet modern communication trends.

The other problems/challenges on disaster media channels of communications identified by the study participants in Mayong and Maynonong are too many

information sources and they cannot pinpoint which one is to be trusted; the lack of capability of the local officials to utilize and maintain appropriate and effective communication channels, incorrect information sent by the agency due to a lack of trust in the source of information, and hard to understand advisories/messages/information due to poor/unclear message delivery.

Preparations to maintain communication during disasters

Respondents were asked to share their experiences on the preparations they have made to maintain communication during disasters/typhoons. Table 13 shows the data for this. Foremost on their list is the purchase of batteries for radios, cell phones, and communication devices, followed by getting the hotline numbers of barangay officials and DRRM officers, the contact numbers of their family members, and the contact numbers of the radio stations. Two other preparations made were securing megaphones and the purchase of a generator for power supply.

Table 13.

Preparations done by the study participants to maintain communication during disasters.

Preparations to ensure communication or access to information during disasters	Mayong		Maynonong		Total	
	number of responses	rank	number of responses	rank	number of responses	rank
Buy batteries for radio, cellphone and other communication devices	153	1	99	3	252	1
Buy generator to ensure continuous supply of power for communication devices	31	5	49	6	80	6
Secure a megaphone	16	6	89	5	105	5
Secure the hotlines of the barangay officials and DRRM officers	110	2	101	2	211	2
Secure the contact numbers of family members	77	3	119	1	196	3
Secure the contact numbers of radio stations	49	4	94	4	143	4

The findings show that both Mayong and Maynonong recognize the importance of utilizing communication tools and devices. The study participants made sure they have batteries or stored power supply that they can use especially when electricity is no longer available. Through these devices, they can contact or communicate with local authorities, such as their barangay officials and DRRM officers. They obtain the contact numbers of their family members to maintain communication with them during a disaster. These are the lifelines that they consider important in crisis communication in their localities.

During emergencies or crises, the use of disaster media as a communication channel/information is necessary. It is considered one of the most important elements of a workplace preparedness plan. President and CEO Bob Boyd of Agility Recovery, a provider of business continuity and disaster recovery solutions, emphasized that not having an effective disaster media communication channel could affect the DRRM strategy of the government. In an emergency, people within an organization must know how to communicate effectively to seek help, saving more lives. It is also necessary to maintain or sustain communication channels during emergencies, crises, or disasters (Maurer. 2015).

Chapter V

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary

This study aimed to determine the disaster media as sources of information messages and their effectiveness on DRMM during disasters in Barangay Mayong and Barangay Maynonong in Tiwi, Albay. The survey approach was used, with questionnaires distributed to study participants. Key informant interviews were also conducted. The total number of respondents was extracted using the Slovin formula. Five research objectives were answered in this study. First, the communication channels utilized by people affected by the disaster as sources of information were identified as well as the community influencers followed by the local community. The majority of the respondents followed foremost their local officials, and then, their family members. They used megaphones, mobile phones, and radios during disasters.

The communication tools and channels utilized in the disaster communication framework or system operating in the Municipality of Tiwi were also identified. The local officials utilized television and cell phones to acquire information.

Second, the study identified SMART and GLOBE as the communication networks active in the study barangays.

Third, the study also identified the preparations made by the respondents before a disaster or typhoon to have communication lines open. Foremost on their list is the purchase of batteries to power up their devices when electricity shuts off. Then, the respondents secure the hotlines of their local officials first, and then the contact numbers of their family members.

Fourth, the respondents rated the effectiveness of the quad media communication channels in making informed decisions about DRRM. Television, radio, and cell phones were “extremely effective” in helping them make informed decisions. Newspapers, social media, and intranet/websites are still considered “very effective” communication channels.

Fifth, the respondents were able to identify the problems and challenges they encountered in using the disaster media channels. The major challenges/problems are as follows: lack of communication networks and service providers, poor/slow internet connection, inefficient use of technology and sources of information, expensive data charges, improper choice of communication channels, and proliferation of fake news,

Conclusions

Based on the salient study findings, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. Television and mobile phones are the most important disaster media communication channels/information sources, while megaphones and radios are the most important communication tools and channels used in the study barangays.
2. SMART and GLOBE are the primary communication networks actively present and operational in the communities.
3. The local officials and family are Tiwi Albay's main social influencers and most socially influential people.

4. The traditional disaster media such as television, radio, cell phone/SMS, and newspapers, and social media (such as FB, Twitter, and YouTube) remain the most dominant and effective disaster media platforms for DRRM in Tiwi, Albay.
5. Different disaster media channels and tools were employed in disseminating information during disasters/typhoons.
6. The respondents identified several problems and challenges they encountered during typhoons and disasters.

Recommendations

In the light of the study findings and conclusions drawn from the study, the recommendations to improve communications during disasters are as follows:

1. Since traditional disaster media communication strategies and programs are vital components of post-disaster recovery, particularly in messaging and information dissemination, it is highly recommended to utilize these types of media. The municipality of Tiwi should develop effective communication strategies and programs utilizing suitable tools that can maximize the potential of these media.
2. Given the findings that the two barangays have limited access to disaster media channels of communication and the absence of an internet connection during disasters/typhoons, it is recommended that local officials should carefully plan access points for such services in anticipation of communication lines being damaged. They should clearly and widely communicate the target location and the specific period for readiness before the disaster so that

residents can also plan in the event of a disaster/typhoon thus saving more lives and property.

3. Considering that local officials and family are Tiwi's main community influencers, it is recommended that local authorities integrate these social influencers into social disaster-media-based communication infrastructure, especially in the emergency preparedness plans, and it should be reflected in the DRRM Plan of Tiwi, Albay.
4. Considering that barangay Mayong and Maynonong had limited disaster media channels and were found to have no clear strategic or coordinated use of these disaster media communications channels for disaster preparedness, it is recommended that the local government develop social media emergency plans that will serve as the first source of reliable information by individuals affected by natural disasters/typhoons.
5. It is also highly recommended that residents in the barangays, especially in remote communities, be educated about alternative communication disaster channels, especially social media to empower and equip them before disasters occur. Educating residents of remote barangays on the value of social media channels will make disaster media more efficient and effective, especially during disasters/typhoons.
6. Considering that disaster-related information/messages are of utmost urgency during disaster/typhoons, it is recommended to set up communication policies that will ensure information is adequately delivered, mechanisms are in place for people to give feedback, and announcements on hazards are immediately received, understood, and processed by the people potentially affected.

LITERATURE CITED

Abid, S. K., Sulaiman, N., Mahmud N. P. N., Nazir, U. & Adnan, N. A. (2020). A Review of The Application Of Remote Sensing And Geographic Information System In Flood Crisis Management, *Journal of Critical Reviews*, 7(16), 491–496.

Adjusters International, (n.d.). Top 10 Communication Methods In A Disaster Setting. <https://www.adjustersinternational.com/newsroom/top-10-communication-methods-in-a-disaster-setting>

Austin, L., & Yan, J. (2010). Social Media and Crisis Communication. Explicating the Social-Mediated Crisis Communication Model. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/316488296_Social_media_and_crisis_communication_Explicating_the_social-mediated_crisis_communication_model

Barrameda, J.T. (2015). Development Practices on Disaster Management For State Universities And Colleges In The Bicol Region. (Unpublished Dissertation). Bicol University Graduate School, Bicol University, Legazpi City.

Becodo, R. P. (2015). Governance Communication for DRRM And Preparedness Level of The Disaster-Prone Communities In Iloilo, Philippines. *Journal of Science and Technology*.

Boholano, C. A. (2013). The Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Capability of The Local Government Unit Of Malilipot In The West District Of Albay. (Unpublished Dissertation). Bicol University Graduate School. Bicol University. Legazpi City

Bongo, P. (2010). Community-Based Communication Systems for Increased Resilience: Experiences From A Disaster Risk Reduction Project In Rural Zimbabwe. In: International Disaster and Risk Conference IDRC Davos 2010, Proceedings, Davos,

Switzerland, 2010.

<https://www.preventionweb.net/english/hyogo/gar/2015/en/bgdocs/inputs/Stal,%202014.%20Disaster%20and%20crisis%20communication%20trend%20analysis%20of%20technologies%20and%20approaches.pdf>

Bradley DT., McFarland M., & Clarke M. (2014). The Effectiveness of Disaster Risk Communication: A Systematic Review Of Intervention Studies. *PLoS Curr.* 22; 6:1. doi: 10.1371/currents.dis.349062e0db1048bb9fc3a3fa67d8a4f8

Center for Security Studies (CSS), ETH Zurich. (2013). 3RG Special Report.

Census of Population (2020). "Region V (Bicol Region)". Total Population by Province, City, Municipality, and Barangay. PSA. <https://psa.gov.ph/content/highlights-region-v-bicol-region-population-2020-census-population-and-housing-2020-cph>.

Centre for Climate Change Economics and Policy Report. (2020). Disaster Impacts and Financing: Local insights from The Philippines. https://www.lse.ac.uk/grantham_institute/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/GRI_policy_report_Disaster-impacts-and-financing_Local-insights-from-the-Philippines.pdf

Center for Excellence in Disaster Management & Humanitarian Assistance. (2018). *Philippines: Disaster reference management handbook*. <https://reliefweb.int/report/philippines/philippines-disaster-management-reference-handbook-march-2018>

CERC: (2014). Crisis and Emergency Risk Communication (Manual): Updated 2014 -- Other Communication Channels. https://emergency.cdc.gov/cerc/ppt/CERC_Other_Communication_Channels.pdf

Chiu, C.M., Hsu, M.H., & Wang, E.T.G. (2006). Understanding Knowledge Sharing in Virtual Communities: An Integration Of Social Capital And Social Cognitive Theories Decision

Support System.

<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/222422090> Understanding Knowledge Sharing in Virtual Communities An Integration of Social Capital and Social Cognitive Theories

Claudy, L. D. (2014). Radio and Television Broadcasting During Disasters.

DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1036/1097-8542.YB150564>

Comfort, L. K., Ko, K., & Zagorecki, A. (2004). Coordination In Rapidly Evolving Disaster Response Systems: The Role Of Information. *Am. Behav. Sci.* 48, 295–313.

doi:10.1177/0002764204268987.

<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/237459868> Coordination in Rapidly Evolving Disaster Response Systems The Role of Information

Communication at Work. (n.d.). Choosing Appropriate Channels.

<https://ecampusontario.pressbooks.pub/communicationatwork/chapter/2-3-selecting-appropriate-channels/>

Conde, M. (2019). Wrong forecast worsened Usman death toll in Bicol—Expert.

<https://www.rappler.com/nation/220380-factor-high-death-toll-bicol-tropical-depression-usman>

Cresswell, J. W. (2014). Research design: *Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches*. 4th Ed. SAGE Publications.

Daep, C. D. (2019, July 13). APSEMO, Albay. Personal interview.

Damo, M. D. (2019, August 4). MDRRMO, Tiwi, Albay. Personal interview.

Devex Editor.(2018). Satellite communications power response to Mayon Volcano.

<https://www.devex.com/news/sponsored/satellite-communications-power-response-to-mayon-volcano-92595>

DSWD DROMIC. (2019). Report #34 on Tropical depression "USMAN" as of 30 January 2019, 4 pm. <https://reliefweb.int/report/philippines/dswd-dromic-report-34-tropical-depression-usman-30-january-2019-4pm>

Ehnis, C., & Bunker, D. (2012). Social Media in Disaster Response: Queensland Police Service – Public Engagement During The 2011 Floods. *Paper Presented at the 23rd Australasian Conference on Information Systems, Geelong, Australia.*
<https://dro.deakin.edu.au/eserv/DU:30049056/ehnis-socialmedia-2012.pdf>

Ellen S. (n.d.) Slovin's Formula Sampling Techniques.
https://www.ehow.co.uk/way_5475547_slovins-formula-sampling-techniques.html

Elsamni, A. (2018). Social Media Applications In Crisis Management Of Natural Disasters: Lessons For The Arab Region.
https://www.academia.edu/36059783/Social_Media_Applications_in_Crisis_Management_of_Natural_Disasters_Lessons_for_the_Arab_Region

Flor, A.G. (2009). Societies in The Information Age: A Critical Perspective. University of The Philippines Open University.

Fraustino, J. D., Brooke, L. & Ya, J. (2012). "Social Media Use During Disasters: A Review of The Knowledge Base And Gaps," Final Report to Human Factors/Behavioral Sciences Division, Science and Technology Directorate, U.S. Department of Homeland Security.

Geysler, W. (2022) What is an influencer? – Social Media Influencers Defined.
<https://influencermarketinghub.com/what-is-an-influencer/>

Globe. (2021, June 1). Reduces Disaster Risks with Robust Business Continuity Program.

<https://www.globe.com.ph/about-us/newsroom/sustainability/reduces-disaster-risks-robust-business-continuity>

Haddow, G., Haddow, K. (2014). Disaster Communications in a Changing Media World. 2nd Edition.

Hale, J., Dulek, R. & Hale, D. (2005). Crisis Response Communication Challenges: Building Theory from Qualitative Data. *International Journal of Business Communication*.
<https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/0021943605274751>

Hurriyet Daily News (2019). Turkey's Marmara Earthquake Is Commemorated on Its 19th Anniversary. <http://www.hurriyetaidailynews.com/turkeys-marmara-earthquake-commemorated-on-19th-anniversary-13589>

International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies. (2006). Philippines Typhoons: Focus on Albay, Catanduanes, and Camarines Sur - Appeal No. MDRPH002. <https://reliefweb.int/report/philippines/philippines-typhoons-focus-albay-catanduanes-and-camarines-sur-appeal-no-mdrph002>

International Telecommunication Union [ITU]. (n.d). ICTs 4 Disaster Management
<https://www.itu.int/en/ITU-D/Emergency-Telecommunications/Pages/ICTs-4-DM.aspx#:~:text=%E2%80%8B%E2%80%8B%E2%80%8B%E2%80%8B%E2%80%8B,operations%20and%20decision%20making%20processes>

Investopedia.com, (2020). Social Media Definition.
<https://www.investopedia.com/terms/s/social-media.asp>

Jha, A., Lin, L., Short, SM., Argentina. G., Gamhewage. G. & Savoia, E. (2018). Integrating Emergency Risk Communication (ERC) into the public health system response: Systematic review of the literature to aid formulation of the 2017 WHO

guideline for ERC policy and practice. *PLoS ONE* 13 (10), e0205555.

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0205555>

Kokemuller, N. (2019). The main differences between social media and TV and radio advertising. <https://smallbusiness.chron.com/main-differences-between-social-media-tv-radio-advertising-61434.html>

Lazer, D., Kennedy, R. & Margolin, D. (2013). Communication in The Aftermath of The Boston Marathon Bombing. <https://repository.library.northeastern.edu/files/neu:330082/fulltext.pdf>

Lynch, C. (2010). Top U.N. aid official critiques Haiti aid efforts in confidential email. *Foreign Policy*, <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3090106/>

Marquez, C. (2019). PAGASA denies claims UP Noah head on 'Usman' 'wrong forecasts' <https://newsinfo.inquirer.net/1073865/pagasa-denies-claims-of-up-noah-head-on-usman-wrong-forecasts>

Maskey, A. (2012) Defining the Community's Role In Disaster Mitigation. Practical Action Technical Brief. <https://www.weadapt.org/knowledge-base/disasters-and-climate-change/defining-the-community's-role-in-disaster-mitigation>

Maurer, R. (2014) Communicate Effectively in A Crisis. <https://www.shrm.org/resourcesandtools/hr-topics/risk-management/pages/communicate-effectively-crisis.aspx>

Mckinney, V., Yoon, K. & Zahedi, F.M. (2002). The Measurement Of Web Customer Satisfaction: An Expectation and Disconfirmation Approach. *Information Systems Research* 13(3), 296-315. <https://pubsonline.informs.org/doi/abs/10.1287/isre.13.3.296.76>

Medford-Davis, L.N. & Kapur, G.B. (2014). Preparing For Effective Communications During Disasters: Lessons from A World Health Organization Quality Improvement Project. *Int J Emerg Med.* 7, 15. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4000058/>

Mehan, P. & Myfellow, R. (2010). The Unprecedented Role of SMS In Disaster Response: Learning from Haiti. https://courses.cs.washington.edu/courses/cse490d/13wi/ClassMaterials/papers/meier_munro.pdf

Mina, R. (2021). Philippines Looks to Improve Disaster Preparedness with Geospatial Technology. Mongabay. <https://news.mongabay.com/2021/03/philippines-looks-to-improve-disaster-preparedness-with-geospatial-tech/#:~:text=At%20least%2060%25%20of%20the , and%20the%20Ring%20of%20Fire>

NASP School Safety and Crisis Response Committee. (2015). Using Social Media Before, During, And After School Crises: Tips for Parents and Educators. Bethesda, MD: National Association of School Psychologists.

Nasta, R. (2019). The role of social media in education. bcnschool.edu.in/blog/social-media-ineducation/#:~:text=The%20use%20of%20social%20media,opportunities%20to%20improve%20learning%20method

Newbythe. (2018). ICT Bayanihan stresses need for communication tools during disasters. <https://newsbytes.ph/2016/07/29/ict-bayanihan-stresses-need-for-communication-tools-during-disasters/>

- Oke, M.O., Adeyinka, A.T., & Oluseyi, O.G. (2018). Media and Disaster Management: Analysing Communication Trends in Flood-Ravaged Communities In Benue, State, North Central Nigeria. *J. Media and Commun. Stud.* 10 (9), 106- 112.
<https://academicjournals.org/journal/JMCS/article-abstract/AA0903E58881>
- Olson, E. K. (2020). Crisis communication in public organizations: Dimensions in Crisis Communications Revisited. *Journal of Contingencies and Crisis Management* 22(2), 113-125. <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/1468-5973.12047>
- Orau.org (2020). Essential Principles of Active Communication.
https://www.orau.gov/hsc/ercwbt/content/ERCcdcenergy/Content/activeinformation/essential_principles/EP-channels.htm
- Paton, D., Johnston, D., Mamula-Seadon, L., and Kenney, C. M. (2014). "Recovery And Development: Perspectives from New Zealand And Australia," in *Disaster & Development: Examining Global Issues and Cases*, eds N. Kapucu and K. T. Liou (New York, NY: Springer), 255–272.
<https://researchers.cdu.edu.au/en/publications/recovery-and-development-perspectives-from-new-zealand-and-australia>
https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-319-04468-2_15
- PhilAtlas. (n.d.). Albay.
<https://www.philatlas.com/luzon/r05/albay/tiwi/mayong.html#:~:text=Historical%20population,population%20of%201%2C632%20in%202015>
- Philippine Statistics Authority. (2020). Bicol Region.
<https://psa.gov.ph/content/highlights-region-v-bicol-region-population-2020-census-population-and-housing-2020-cph>
- Rangasa, M. C. (2019, July 13). Personal interview.

Recuenco, A. (2018). Authorities waging war vs. fake volcanologists on social media.

Manila Bulletin. <https://news.mb.com.ph/2018/01/21/authorities-waging-war-vs-fake-volcanologists-in-social-media/>

Republic Act No. 10121. Philippine Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Act of 2010. <https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/2010/05/27/republic-act-no-10121/>

Republic Act No. 7160. Local Government Code of 1991. <https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/1991/10/10/republic-act-no-7160/>

Robbins, J.P. (n.d.), Risk Transfer and Disaster Management. <https://preparecenter.org/topic/risk-transfer/>

Sahana, M. & Sajjad H. (2019). Vulnerability to Storm Surge Flood Using Remote Sensing and GIS Techniques: A Study on Sundarban biosphere reserve remote sensing. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rsase.2018.10.008>

Sahin, M. & Ergin, T. (2000). The August 17 Kocaeli and the November 12 Duzce Earthquakes in Turkey. *Earth, Planets and Space* 52, 753=757. <https://earth-planets-space.springeropen.com/articles/10.1186/BF03352277>

Sakurai, M. & Murayama, Y. (2019). Information Technologies and Disaster Management – Benefits And Issues. – <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pdisas.2019.100012>

Salceda, J. S. (2013). Zero casualty: DRRM in Albay. Paper presented in Global Public Innovations Conference. <https://docplayer.net/89630100-Zero-casualty-drrm-in-albay.html>

Sarmienta, S. Jr. (2015). The Typhoon Preparedness Communication of Albay Province: A Case Study.

<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/281289028> The Typhoon Prepare
dness Communication of Albay Province A Case Study

Seeger, M. W., Sellnow, T. L. & Ulmer, R. R. (2016). Communication, Organization and
Crisis. *Annals of the International Communications Association*.
<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/23808985.1998.11678952>

SMART. (2017). Communities Benefit from Smart's Disaster Preparedness,
Environmental Programs. [https://smart.com.ph/About/newsroom/press-
releases/2017/12/21/communities-benefit-from-smart-s-disaster-preparedness-
environment-programs](https://smart.com.ph/About/newsroom/press-releases/2017/12/21/communities-benefit-from-smart-s-disaster-preparedness-environment-programs)

Stibich, Mark (2024). The Psychology of Religion Why do we believe?
[https://www.verywellmind.com/religion-improves-health-
2224007#:~:text=Religion%20can%20be%20a%20source,that%20it%20may
%20affect%20health.](https://www.verywellmind.com/religion-improves-health-2224007#:~:text=Religion%20can%20be%20a%20source,that%20it%20may%20affect%20health.)

Suleyman, S., & Corbacioglu. S. (2010). Role Of Information In Collective Action In
Dynamic Disaster Environments. *Disasters* 34, (1), 137-154.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-7717.2009.01118.x>

Swati Kumari. 2019. Impact of ICT and Social Media on Society
Relationship. <https://www.jetir.org/papers/JETIR1901555.pdf>

Tanvir, Claudine Claridad (2015) "Education For Disaster Risk Reduction Toward Change:
The Case Of The 'Climate Change Academy' In Albay Province, Philippines,"
Journal of Social Sciences: Vol. 45: Iss. 1, Article 9.
<https://digital.car.chula.ac.th/cujss/vol45/iss1/9>

Techopedia.com. (n.d.). Media. <https://techopedia.com/definition/1088/media>

Tracy, T. (2022). Facebook's advantage over other social media. *Investopedia*.

<https://www.investopedia.com/articles/company-insights/070216/what-facebooks-advantage-over-other-social-media-fb.asp>

Trevor, G. (2016). Barriers To Communicating Disaster Response Information To The Public During Disaster Situations. Bachelor of Architectural Science, MSc. Disaster Management and Sustainable Development (with commendation) Aus Scarborough, Kanada. <file:///C:/Users/user/Downloads/PhD%20Thesis.pdf>

United Nations Economic and Social Commission for Asia and the Pacific. (2016).

Disasters in Asia and the Pacific: 2015 in review.
https://www.unescap.org/sites/default/files/2015_Year%20in%20Review_final_PDF_1.pdf

United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs. (2019).

Philippines: Tropical depression Usman affects 191,600 people and displaces 79,600. <https://www.unocha.org/story/philippines-tropical-depression-usman-affects-191600-people-and-displaces-79600>

United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs. (2014).

Communications with communities: Response to Typhoon Haiyan (Yolanda)
<https://www.unocha.org/publications/report/philippines/communications-communities-response-typhoon-haiyan-yolanda-11-april-2014>

United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction. (2017) Public communication for disaster risk reduction.

[https://www.preventionweb.net/files/52828_apubliccommunication\[1\].pdf](https://www.preventionweb.net/files/52828_apubliccommunication[1].pdf)

Using ICT And Social Media in Disasters: Opportunities and Risks For Government.

https://css.ethz.ch/content/dam/ethz/special-interest/gess/cis/center-for-securities-studies/pdfs/Opportunities_and_Risks_for_Government.pdf

Vanevska, A. (n.d.) What Is Your Influencer Community and Why Is It Important. *Afluencer*.

ext=Influencers%20are%20at%20the%20core,they%20post%20about%20your%20br

and Warning Tweets: Serial Transmission Of Messages During The Warning Phase Of

A Disaster Event. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/1369118X.2013.862561>

ANNEX A

The Questionnaire/Survey Form (English)

UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES
OPEN UNIVERSITY
Faculty of Information and Communication Studies

Greetings!

The undersigned is conducting a study on **Quad Media as Sources of Disaster Messages and their Effectiveness to DRRM in Albay** as a requirement to complete her masteral degree in Development Communication. May I request for your honest and complete answers to the following questions in this questionnaire. Rest assured that all information stated in this questionnaire shall be treated only for the said purpose and with utmost confidentiality.

Sincerely yours,

MAYFLOR MARIE L. JUMAMIL
Researcher

Questionnaire No. ____

Quad Media as Sources of Disaster Messages and their Effectiveness to DRRM in Albay

Name: _____ Age: _____
Occupation: _____ Sex: _____
Address: _____

I – Channels and Tools of Communication. Which of these channels of communication/ sources of information provide you the needed disaster information/messages?

A. Channels

Channels of Communication/ Sources of Information	Please tick/check. (You may choose more than one.)
Newspaper	
Radio	
TV (television)	
Cellphone/SMS	
Internet/Websites	
Social Media (FB, Twitter, Youtube)	
Immediate/Nearest Neighbor	
Kumpare/Kumare	
Family	
Local Officials	
Religious Leaders	

B. Tools

Which of these communication tools or devices your local officials use to relay information to the community during disasters?

B. Tools

Which of these communication tools or devices your local officials use to relay information to the community during disasters?

Communication tools/devices utilized during disasters	Please tick/check. (You may choose more than one.)
Megaphone	
Cellphone	
Radio	
Handheld Radio (Walkie-Talkie/VHF)	
Others (please specify)	

B.1. Tools used during the Tropical Depression Usman. What were the communication tools or devices your barangay officials used to relay information during the Tropical Depression Usman last December 29, 2018?

Communication tools/devices utilized during disasters	Please tick/check. (You may choose more than one.)
Megaphone	
Cellphone	
Radio	
Handheld Radio (Walkie-Talkie/VHF)	
Others (please specify)	

II. Frequency of Use. A. Please put a check (/) mark on the item that signifies how often you access or utilizes these media/channels to receive and share information **during disasters**. (You may choose more than one)

Please rate the following degree of frequency using this scale:

- 5 – Always (at all times)
- 4 – Almost always (oftentimes)
- 3 – Sometimes
- 2 – Seldom
- 1 – Never

Channels of Communication/ Sources of Information	FREQUENCY				
	5	4	3	2	1
Newspaper					
Radio					
TV (television)					
Cellphone/SMS (ICT)					
Internet/Websites (ICT)					
Social Media (FB, Twitter, Youtube)					
Immediate/Nearest Neighbor					
Kumpare/Kumare					
Family					
Local Officials					
Religious Leaders					
Others					

B. - Please put a check (/) mark on the item that signifies how often you access or utilizes these media/channels to receive and share information **during the Tropical Depression Usman**. (You may choose more than one)

Please rate the following degree of frequency using this scale:

- 5 – Always (at all times)
- 4 – Almost always (oftentimes)
- 3 – Sometimes
- 2 – Seldom
- 1 – Never

Channels of Communication/ Sources of Information	FREQUENCY				
	5	4	3	2	1
Newspaper					
Radio					
TV (television)					
Cellphone/SMS (ICT)					
Internet/Websites (ICT)					
Social Media (FB, Twitter, Youtube)					
Immediate/Nearest Neighbor					
Kumpare/Kumare					
Family					
Local Officials					
Religious Leaders					
Others					

III – Effectiveness of Communication Channels

A. Timeliness. Please rate these media/channels of communication in providing you with **TIMELY** information to help you in decision-making in times of disaster. Please check the item.

Channels of Communication/ Sources of Information	Very Timely (5)	Moderately Timely (4)	Timely (3)	Less timely (2)	Not Timely (1)
Newspaper					
Radio					
TV (television)					
Cellphone/SMS					
Internet/Websites					
Social Media (FB, Twitter, Youtube)					
Immediate/Nearest Neighbor					
Kumpare/Kumare					
Family					
Local Officials					
Religious Leaders					
Others					

B. Accuracy. Please rate these media/channels of communication in helping you in access **ACCURATE** information to help you in decision-making in times of disaster. Please check the item.

Channels of Communication/ Sources of Information	Very Accurate (5)	Mode- rately Accurate (4)	Timely (3)	Less Accurate (2)	Not Accurate (1)
Newspaper					
Radio					
TV (television)					
Cellphone/SMS					
Internet/Websites					
Social Media (FB, Twitter, Youtube)					
Immediate/Nearest Neighbor					
Kumpare/Kumare					
Family					
Local Officials					
Religious Leaders					
Others					

C. Relevance. Please rate these media/channels of communication that provides **RELEVANT** information to help you in decision-making in times of disaster? Please check the item.

Channels of Communication/ Sources of Information	Very Relevant (5)	Moderately Relevant (4)	Relevant (3)	Less Relevant (2)	Not Relevant (1)
Newspaper					
Radio					
TV (television)					
Cellphone/SMS					
Internet/Websites					
Social Media (FB, Twitter, Youtube)					
Immediate/Nearest Neighbor					
Kumpare/Kumare					
Family					
Local Officials					
Religious Leaders					
Others					

D. Understandability. Please rate these media/channels of communication in providing you **UNDERSTANDABLE** information to help you in decision-making in times of disaster. Please check the item.

Channels of Communication/ Sources of Information	Very Understandable (5)	Moderately Understandable (4)	Understandable (3)	Less Understandable (2)	Not Understandable (1)
Newspaper					
Radio					
TV(television)					
Cellphone/SMS					
Internet/Websites					
Social Media (FB, Twitter, Instagram)					
Immediate/Nearest Neighbor					
Kumpare/Kumare					
Family					
Local Officials					
Religious Leaders					

IV- Active Communication Networks. What are the available or active communication networks operating or has a signal in your community?

Communication Networks operating in the community	Please tick/check. (You may choose more than one.)
SMART	
GLOBE	
PLDT	
DCTV	
Others (pls specify)	

V – Crisis Communication Challenges. The following factors can be perceived as hindrance for an effective communication and DRRM responses during a disaster. These can also be considered challenges in utilizing the communication channels. Please put a check (/) mark on the item/s that you think are also true per experience. (You may choose more than one).

Crisis Communication Challenges	Please tick/check. (You may choose more than one.)
There is a lack of communication networks or service providers in the locality	
When using the internet, cellphone and social media, there is a poor/slow connection	
Social Media cannot be accessed due to expensive data connection.	
Only radio can be accessed during a disaster for a while due to termination of power supply and inefficient use of technology by the sources of information	
When radio, tv, social media cannot be accessed, information is sought from neighbors and kins (poor choice of communication channels)	
There is proliferation of fake news.	
There are too many information sources and cannot identify which one is to be trusted.	
The advisories/messages/information cannot be understood. (Poor/unclear message delivery)	
The agency/agencies sending the information shares incorrect information (lack of trust to the information source)	
Local officials do not have a capability to use and maintain appropriate and effective communication channels	
Others: (please specify)	

VI. Preparations to Maintain Communication During Disasters. – What are the preparations you do in order for you to ensure that you can access information during disasters?

Preparations to ensure communication or access to information during disasters	Please tick/check. (You may choose more than one.)
Buy batteries for radio, cellphone and other communication devices	
Buy generator to ensure continuous supply of power for communication devices	
Secure a megaphone	
Secure the hotlines of the barangay officials and DRRM officers	
Secure the contact numbers of family members	
Secure the contact numbers of radio stations	
Others (Please specify)	

THANK YOU!

Interview Guide

I. Agenda Setting / Introduction of Interviewer

II. Interview Questions

1. Are you aware of the different risks and threats during disasters in your community? Why or why not?
2. Why do you think TD Usman affected (or did not affect) your barangay?
3. Is there a disaster communication protocol in your barangay? How have you come to know about it?
4. How is this communication protocol relayed to the barangay constituents?
5. How did your local officials respond before and after TD Usman with regards to communicating with you?
6. How do you think people should be informed in times of disasters?
7. Do you think PAGASA, PHIVOLCS, NDRRMC/BDRRMC and other government agencies which are authorities for disasters trustworthy? Why or why not?
8. How was life after Tropical Usman affected your community?
9. How were you able to cope up with the effects of TD Usman?
10. When calamities and disasters happen, what comes into your mind?
11. If the government would advise you to relocate, would you heed and leave your place? Why or why not?

III. Closing and appreciation

Note: Questions may be delivered in the vernacular.

ANNEX B

The Questionnaire/Survey Form (Vernacular/Bicol-Albay)

UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES
OPEN UNIVERSITY
Faculty of Information and Communication Studies

Sarong pagbati nin marhay na aldaw!

An saindong lingkod presenting nagaadal para sa saiyang Thesis na may titulong **Quad Media as Sources of Disaster Messages and their Effectiveness to DRRM in Albay** bilang saro sa mga rekisitos para sa saiyang masteral degree sa Development Communication. Katakod kaini, nakikihuron po siya para sa saindong partisipasyon sa pag-aadal na nasambit sa paagi kan pagsimbag nin honesto asin kumpleto sa mga kahaputan na yaon digdi sa questionnaire. Laoman po nindu na gabos na impormasyon na nakalaag digdi gagamiton sana sa katuyuhan kan pag-aadal asin kurso na ini asin ita-tratar na kumpedensyal.

An minagalang,

MAYFLOR MARIE L. JUMAMIL
Researcher

Questionnaire No. ____

Quad Media as Sources of Disaster Messages and their Effectiveness to DRRM in Albay
(An Quad Media Bilang Pighahalian kan Disaster Messages asin an Pagiging Epektibo kaini sa DRRM sa Albay)

Pangaran: _____ Edad: _____
Trabaho: _____ Seks: _____
Address: _____

I – Channels and Tools of Communication (Mga Channel asin Kagamitan Para sa Komunikasyon). Arin sa mga minasunod na channel kan komunikasyon o pighahalian kan impormasyon an nakapagtatao saimo nin mga kinakaipuhan na impormasyon manongod sa kalamidad o disaster?

A. Channels

Mga Channel asin Kagamitan Para sa Komunikasyon	Tsekan kun arin. (Pwedeng magpili nin sobra sa saro)
Peryodiko	
Radyo	
TV (telebisyon)	
Cellphone/SMS	
Internet/Websites	
Social Media (FB, Twitter, Youtube)	
Pinakaraning kapitbahay	
Kumpare/Kumare	
Pariantes	
Mga Lokal na Opisyal	
Mga Taga-pamayo sa Relihiyon	

B. Tools (Kagamitan)

Arin sa mga kagamitan na ini sa komunikasyon an ginagamit kan saindong mga local na opisyal sa paghahtod nin impormasyon sa saindong kumunidad kun may kalamidad?

Mga Kagamitan na ginagamit kun may kalamidad	Tsekan kun arin. (Pwedeng magpili nin sobra sa sarong)
Megaphone	
Cellphone	
Radyo	
Handheld Radio (Walkie-Talkie/VHF)	
Iba pa (Sambiton)	

B.1. Mga kagamitan sa komunikasyon na ginamit durante kan Tropical Depression Usman. Ano-ano an mga kagamitan sa komunikasyon na ginamit kan saindong mga batangay officials sa pagpapaabot nin impormasyon durante kan Tropical Depression Usman kan nakaaging Disyembre 29, 2018?

Mga Kagamitan na ginamit sa kalamidad durante kan TD Usman	Tsekan kun arin. (Pwedeng magpili nin sobra sa sarong)
Megaphone	
Cellphone	
Radyo	
Handheld Radio (Walkie-Talkie/VHF)	
Iba pa (Sambiton)	

II. Frequency of Use (Kalimitan kan Paggamit.) A. Markahan nin tsek an mga bagay base sa kalimitan kan paggamit tanganing maka-resibe asin makatao nin impormasyon kun may kalamidad. (Pwedeng magpili nin sobra sa saro.)

Gamiton an mga minasunod na marka:

- 5 – Always (at all times)/Ginagamit sa gabos na panahon
- 4 – Almost always (oftentimes)/Kalimitan na ginagamit
- 3 – Sometimes/Minsan na ginagamit
- 2 – Seldom/Bihirang Gamiton
- 1 – Never/Dai Ginagamit

Mga Channel asin Pighahalian nin Impormasyon	FREQUENCY/KALIMITAN				
	5	4	3	2	1
Peryodiko					
Radyo					
TV (telebisyon)					
Cellphone/SMS					
Internet/Websites					
Social Media (FB, Twitter, Youtube)					
Pinakaraning kapitbahay					
Kumpare/Kumare					
Pariantes					
Mga Lokal na Opisyal					
Mga Taga-pamayo sa Relihiyon					
Iba pa					

B. – Markahan nin tsek an mga bagay base sa kalimitan kan paggamit tanganing maka-resibe asin makatao nin impormasyon durante kan **Tropical Depression Usman**. (Pwedeng magpili nin sobra sa saro.)

Gamiton an mga minasunod na marka:

- 5 – Always (at all times)/ Ginagamit sa gabos na Panahon
- 4 – Almost always (oftentimes)/Kalimitan na ginagamit
- 3 – Sometimes/Minsan na ginagamit
- 2 – Seldom/Bihirang Gamiton
- 1 – Never/Dai Ginagamit

Mga Channel asin Pighahalian nin Impormasyon	FREQUENCY/KALIMITAN				
	5	4	3	2	1
Peryodiko					
Radyo					
TV (telebisyon)					
Cellphone/SMS					
Internet/Websites					
Social Media (FB, Twitter, Youtube)					
Pinakaraning kapitbahay					
Kumpare/Kumare					
Parientes					
Mga Lokal na Opisyal					
Mga Taga-pamayo sa Relihiyon					
Iba pa					

III – Effectiveness of Communication Channels (Pagiging Epektibo kan mga Channel kan Komunikasyon)

A. Tama sa Oras (Timeliness.) Markahan nin tsek an mga bagay base sa kapanahunan o pagiging tama sa oras na makapagtao saimo nin impormasyon para matabangan ka makapagdesisyon sa panahon nin kalamidad. (Pwedeng magpili nin sobra sa sarong.)

Mga Channel asin Pighahalian nin Impormasyon	Tamang-Tama Sa oras (Very Timely) (5)	Medyo Tama sa Oras (Moderately Timely) (4)	Tama sa Oras (Timely) (3)	Diit na tama sa Oras (Less Timely) (2)	Dai Tama sa Oras (Not Timely) (1)
Peryodiko					
Radyo					
TV (telebisyon)					
Cellphone/SMS					
Internet/Websites					
Social Media (FB, Twitter, Youtube)					
Pinakaraning kapitbahay					
Kumpare/Kumare					
Pariantes					
Mga Lokal na Opisyal					
Mga Taga-pamayo sa Relihiyon					
Iba pa					

B. Kasyertuhan (Accuracy.) Markahan nin tsek an mga bagay base sa makapagtatao saimo nin syerto o tamang impormasyon para matabangan ka makapagdesisyon sa panahon nin kalamidad. (Pwedeng magpili nin sobra sa saro.)

Mga Channel asin Pighahalian nin Impormasyon	Syertuhon /Tamaon	Medyo Syerto/Tama	Syerto/Tamalang	Bako Masyado Syerto	Bako Syerto
	Very Accurate (5)	Moderately Accurate (4)	Accurate (3)	Less Accurate (2)	Not Accurate (1)
Peryodiko					
Radyo					
TV (telebisyon)					
Cellphone/SMS					
Internet/Websites					
Social Media (FB, Twitter, Youtube)					
Pinakaraning kapitbahay					
Kumpare/Kumare					
Parientes					
Mga Lokal na Opisyal					
Mga Taga-pamayo sa Relihiyon					
Iba pa					

C. Relevance (Importante asin Napapanahon.) Markahan nin tsek an mga bagay base sa makapagtatao saimo nin importante asin napapanahon na impormasyon para matabangan ka makapagdesisyon sa panahon nin kalamidad. (Pwedeng magpili nin sobra sa saro.)

Mga Channel asin Pighahalian nin Impormasyon	Very Relevant (5)	Moderately Relevant (4)	Relevant (3)	Less Relevant (2)	Not Relevant (1)
Peryodiko					
Radyo					
TV (telebisyon)					
Cellphone/SMS					
Internet/Websites					
Social Media (FB, Twitter, Youtube)					
Pinakaraning kapitbahay					
Kumpare/Kumare					
Parientes					
Mga Lokal na Opisyal					
Mga Taga-pamayo sa Relihiyon					
Iba pa					

D. Nasasabutan (Understandability/Understandable.) Markahan nin tsek an mga bagay base sa makapagtatao saimo nin nasasabutan na impormasyon para matabangan ka makapagdesisyon sa panahon nin kalamidad. (Pwedeng magpili nin sobra sa saro.)

Mga Channel asin Pighahalian nin Impormasyon	Nasasabutan nin Maray Very Understandable (5)	Medyo Nasasabutan Moderately Understandable (4)	Nasasabutan Understandable (3)	Diit na nasasabutan Less Understandable (2)	Dai Nasasabutan Not Understandable (1)
Peryodiko					
Radyo					
TV (telebisyon)					
Cellphone/SMS					
Internet/Websites					
Social Media (FB, Twitter, Youtube)					
Pinakaraning kapitbahay					
Kumpare/Kumare					
Parientes					
Mga Lokal na Opisyal					
Mga Taga-pamayo sa Relihiyon					
Iba pa					

IV- Active Communication Networks (Mga Aktibong Network sa Kumunikasyon.) Ano ano an mga network sa komunikasyon an aktibo, may signal o nag-ooperate sa saindang kumunidad?

Mga Aktibong Network sa Kumunikasyon	Tsekan kun arin. (Pwedeng magpili nin sobra sa saro)
SMART	
GLOBE	
PLDT	
DCTV	
Iba pa (pls specify)	

V – Crisis Communication Challenges (Mga Agyat sa Kumunikasyon kun may Krisis o Kalamidad.) An mga minasunod mga posibleng kadahilanan na nakakaulang sa epektibong komunikasyon asin pagresponde kan DRRM sa panahon nin mga kalamidad. Tsekan an mga bagay na sa hiling mo totoo base sa saimong eksperyensa. (Pwedeng magpili nin sobra sa saro.)

Mga Agyat sa Kumunikasyon kun may Krisis o Kalamidad	Tsekan kun arin. (Pwedeng magpili nin sobra sa saro)
May kakulangan nin network sa komunikasyon (communication networks) o tagapagtao nin serbisyo sa komunikasyon (service providers) sa kumunidad.	
Mabagal an koneksyon sa paggamit kan internet/social media, cellphone.	
Mahal o magastos an "data connection" sa pagkonektar sa internet/social media.	
Solamenteng radyo sana an pwedeng dangugon kun may kalamidad dahil sa pagpundo kan serbisyo sa kuryente o bakong episyenteng paggamit kan teknolohiya kan mga pighahalian kan impormasyon.	
Kun dai na makakakua nin impormasyon sa radio, tv, social media, an impormasyon kukuanon na sana sa mga kataraning o mga parientes.	
May paglalaganap nin pekeng impormasyon (fake news.)	
Igwa nin dakulon na mga pighahalian nin impormasyon o "information sources" asin dai madeterminar kun arin an mapagkakatwalaan.	
Dai masabutan an mga abiso/mensahe/impormasyon na pigpapaluwas.	
Sala an mga pigpapaluwas na impormasyon kan mga pighahalian kaini.	
Mayong kapabilidad an mga local na opisya sa paggamit asin pag mantenir kan mga tama asin epektibong channel nin komunikasyon.	
Iba pa: (sambiton)	

VI. Preparations to Maintain Communication During Disasters (Mga Preparasyon para Mamantenir an Komunikasyon Kun may Kalamidad.) – Ano-ano an mga pigigibong preparasyon tanging ma-asegurar mo na may makukua kan impormasyon kun may kalamidad?

Mga Preparasyon para Mamantenir an Komunikasyon Kun may Kalamidad	Tsekan kun arin. (Pwedeng magpili nin sobra sa saro)
Magbakal nin mga bateriya para sa radio, cellphone asin iba pang gamit sa pakikipag-komunikasyon.	
Magbakal nin generator para maka-asegurar na igwa nin dire-diretsong suplay nin kuryente para sa mga gamit sa komunikasyon	
Magpaseguro nin megaphone	
Magpaseguro kan mga hotlines o contact numbers kan mga opisyal kan barangay asin DRRM	
Magpaseguro kan contact numbers kan mga parientes	
Magpaseguro kan contact numbers kan mga istasyon nin radio	
Iba pa (Sambiton)	

SALAMAT PO!

Interview Guide

I. Agenda Setting / Introduction of Interviewer

II. Interview Questions

1. Are you aware of the different risks and threats in your community during disasters? Why or why not? (*Aram mo ba an mga peligro o banta sa saindong komunidad kun may kalamidad? Nata?Nata Dai?*)
2. Why do you think TD Usman affected (or did not affect) your barangay? (*Ano sa hiling mo kun nata naapektuhan/o dai naapektuhan an saindong barangay kan TD Usman?*)
3. Is there a disaster communication protocol in your barangay? How have you come to know about it? (*Igwa ban in pigsusunod na protocol o mga kapaagihan na susundon an saindong barangay kun may kalamidad? Paano mo ini naisihan?*)
4. How Is this communication protocol relayed to the barangay constituents? (*Pa'no ining mga kapaagihan na susundon pigpaaram sa mga konstituentas kan barangay?*)
5. How did your local officials respond before and after TD Usman with regards to communicating with you? (*Pa'no an pagresponde kan saindong mga local na opisyal bago/antes asin pakatapos kan TD Usman sa lado kan pakikipag-komunikasyon saindo?*)
6. How do you think people should be informed in times of disasters? (*Sa hiling mo, pa'no dapat na impormaran an mga tao sa panahon nin kalamidad?*)
7. Do you think PAGASA, PHIVOLCS, NDRRMC/BDRRMC and other government agencies which are authorities for disasters trustworthy? Why or why not? (*Sa hiling mo, mapagkakatiwalaan ba an PAGASA, PHIVOLCS, NDRRMC/BDRRMC asin iba pang ahensya kan gobyerno na may awtoridad sa kalamidad? Nata? Nata dai?*)
8. How was life after Tropical Usman affected your community? (*Kumusta an saindong pagbuhay matapos maapektaran kan TD Usman an saindong komunidad?*)
9. How were you able to cope up with the effects of TD Usman? (*Pa'no kamo nakaraos sa epektong dara ni TD Usman?*)
10. When calamities and disasters happen, what comes into your mind? (*Kun igwa nin kalamidad, ano an naisip nindu?*)
11. If the government would advise you to relocate, would you heed and leave your place? Why or why not? (*Kun papahaliun kamo kan gobyerno sa saindong pinag-iirokan para irelokar, masunod kamo? Nata? Nata dai?*)

III. Closing and appreciation

Note: Questions may be delivered in the vernacular.

ANNEX C

Interview Documentation

Interview with the Municipal Disaster Risk and Reduction Management Officer
of Tiwi, Albay, Manuel D. Damo/August 4, 2019.

Interviews with some locales of the communities of Mayong and Maynonong